

[YEAR 1 EVALUATION]

[Deliverable 6.3]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE/PURPOSE/OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

Deliverable 6.3 presents an evaluation of the first year of the ER4STEM project. The primary aim of this deliverable is to provide baseline data for the analysis of the Framework in project years 2 and 3. The secondary aim is to inform the development of the Framework and Activity Plans. This deliverable presents data from 48 workshops implemented in four European countries by project partners. The evaluation is not intended to be exhaustive and analysis of year 1 data will continue in project year 2 in tandem with the development of the Framework. Analysis of the data occurs at four levels and from these, 11 recommendations for the Evaluation, Activity Plans, Repository and Framework are made for the start of project year 2.

1.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

Deliverable 6.3 draws on data collected from workshops (WP2) conferences and competitions (WP3). The data were collected through the evaluation pre-kit (D6.1) and a modified version during the competition. While the primary aim of this deliverable is to present baseline data with which to analyse years 2 and 3 of the project, the secondary aim of this deliverable is to inform the development of the Framework (WP1) and Activity Plans (WP4). These developments should impact the design and implementation of workshops and conferences and competitions (WP2 & WP3) in years 2 and 3 of the project, through which data will then be collected and evaluated with reference to the baseline data presented here. Ultimately these will all impact the design and use of the repository (WP5).

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

Following a brief introduction to the report, an overview of the data collection and analysis approach is presented in the methodology. Analysis of the data occurs at four levels which provide the structure for the presentation of the finding through four sections. The discussion considers the findings across the four levels and from this arise a series of recommendations for the Framework, Activity Plans and Evaluation for project years 2 and 3.

2 INTRODUCTION

Throughout the first year of the ER4STEM project, workshops were implemented by 5 project partners in 4 countries. As part of each workshop the evaluation pre-kit (D6.1) was implemented in whole or part. The evaluation pre-kit had two roles: The first was to collect baseline data which would be used to evaluate the development and implementation of the ER4STEM Framework in years 2 and 3 of the project. The second was to pilot the evaluation protocol that would be used in years 2 and 3. As part of D6.2, the pre-kit is assessed against these targets. In addition the pre-kit provided data to inform the development of the Framework (WP1) and Activity Plan (WP4).

This report presents the emerging findings from the analysis of data collected using the pre-kit over 48 workshops. In addition to the workshops, a version of the evaluation pre-kit was created for the ECER conference. This report presents the results of the baseline data, the intended outcome of this report. D6.2 provides an assessment of the evaluation pre-kit as part of the report on the development of the final evaluation kit to be used in years 2 and 3 of the project. In addition, due to the breadth of data successfully collected by all partners, several in-depth case studies are presented. These provide findings which not only provides a nuanced understanding of the baseline data but also provide key recommendations for the development of the Evaluation Kit, Framework and Activity Plan:

1. Use 21st Century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills.
2. Consider creativity as leading to innovation and entrepreneurship
3. Examine critical thinking through a focus on reflective thinking
4. Provide evidence of learning
5. Differentiate activities
6. Develop new entry points
7. Develop approaches to the orchestration of teamwork, with particular consideration of mixed-gender groups
8. Evaluate the impact of specific tools
9. Change and sustain attitudes to STEM
10. Raise awareness of pedagogic strategies and their impact
11. Gender-balance the Draw-a-Scientist activity

The pre-kit was designed cognisant of the fact that data would be collected by partners who, on the whole, have no previous experience of research and data collection. Therefore there was an assumption that there may be some difficulties and not all workshops would result in complete data sets. However an unexpected outcome was that the majority of workshops resulted in complete or almost complete data sets. It should therefore be noted that not all data collected has been analysed and that this is an ongoing process. The case-studies presented in this report have been specifically selected to represent the range of findings emerging from the research. Moving into project year 2, as questions arise through work on the development of the Framework and Activity Plan, data from year 1 will be analysed in response to these emerging questions.

2.1 BASELINE QUESTIONS

The baseline questions identified in D6.1 provided the basis for the design of the evaluation pre-kit and will be discussed and answered in this report. They are presented here for reference by project objective:

Objective 1: ER4STEM will approach and engage children by offering multiple entry points into creative STEM (STEAM) via robotics

- Are there multiple entry points facilitated through the ER4STEM framework?
- Do the activities allow learners to connect robots to their personal interests?
- Do children share their ideas with/through these tangible artefacts?
- Do they learn basic scientific concepts?

Objective 2: ER4STEM will offer educational methods for educational robotics to engage all young learners

- Do the activities encourage interest in STEM education?
- Do the activities encourage interest in STEM careers?
- Do the approaches/activities appeal to girls?
- Do girls engage with challenges or let boys 'take over'?
- Are girls interested in the STEM topics?
- Are popular gender stereotypes held? Are they changed?
- Did they participate in collaborative work?
- Were those who were not interested in STEM inspired by their peers?

Objective 3: ER4STEM will study real-world societal problems as perceived by each child and relate societal challenges to existing technologies and required innovations

- Did children identify and define problems that influence their lives?
- Were they equipped with the necessary skills to solve these?
- Do they have an opportunity to present their ideas and artefacts to each other as 'proper' scientists?
- Do they develop 'soft-skills'?
- Do they learn intrarelational (how well they know themselves) and interpersonal skills?

2.2 EVALUATION CRITERIA

In addition to the ER4STEM project objectives, a set of topics for consideration in relation to the aims of the framework were identified:

- Learner engagement
- Changing & sustaining attitudes to STEM
- Connecting STEM to society
- Creativity
- Collaborative working
- Entrepreneurial activity
- Questions for using specific tools
- Evaluate teacher use of ER repository
- What works, for whom and in what circumstances?
- Plans for further development of activities.

The intention was for these to be evaluated using the evaluation kit in years 2 and 3 of the project. In the first year of the project the only objective in relation to these was the piloting of the pre-kit. However, they also provide a useful frame for discussion of the workshops without the ER4STEM Framework, identifying areas of particular importance in the development of the Framework and Activity Plans. From this discussion, recommendations are made not only for the Framework and Activity Plans but also the focus of the year 2 and 3 evaluation.

3 METHODOLOGY

A concurrent, mixed-method research approach was identified as most appropriate to the range of research contexts. These ranged from a single-day 8hr workshop to a workshop implemented over several lessons, to the same workshop implemented with multiple groups of students. Workshops would often be implemented in rapid succession and therefore there would be no opportunity to analyse the data between sessions to inform subsequent data collection in that workshop. Therefore a concurrent approach was most suitable. Qualitative data and analysis are generally given primacy, however a broadly pragmatic approach is taken depending on the research question being addressed.

This section briefly outlines the data collection approach which is presented in detail in D6.1, along with an overview of the data collected. This is followed by the analysis approaches taken.

3.1 EVALUATION CONTEXT: WORKSHOPS AND CONFERENCE OVERVIEW

In total 1213 students participated in 48 workshops in year 1. With 660 male and 553 female students spread across all partners. A further 178 students participated in the ECER conference and competition. At the conference 12 students teams presented a paper and there were 6 students invited to give an individual presentation.

We see that on average participants responded positively when asked how many stars they would give the workshop that they attended, out of 5 (Table 1), while Table 2 shows that there was little variation between genders. At a surface level this suggests that on the whole students strongly enjoyed their experience.

Table 1 Average number of stars out of 5 by partner

Partner	Number of Participants	Average
TU Wien	123	4.18
ESICEE	326	4.90
PRIA	227	4.30
UoA	168	4.59
Across Limits	114	4.67

Table 2 Average number of stars out of 5 by partner, broken down by gender

Partner	Number of Participants	Average
TU Wien		
Female	77	4.21

Male	46	4.12
ESICEE		
Female	154	4.94
Male	172	4.87
PRIA		
Female	102	4.22
Male	125	4.36
UoA		
Female	86	4.56
Male	82	4.62
Across Limits		
Female	58	4.44
Male	56	4.92

3.2 DATA COLLECTION

As outlined in the pre-kit (D6.1) in detail, a mixed-method approach to data collection was identified as most suitable for this project. Qualitative data takes primacy as it allows for the necessary depth of analysis required to identify areas for the development of the Framework. However it is also necessary to evidence similarities or differences between this and existing research into educational robotics. That research has largely taken a quantitative approach to data collection and although it has provided some evidence on the outcomes of engaging in educational robotics activities, at best it is limited to identifying what happens (within the range of questions asked). Without qualitative data we cannot begin to explain why or how, which are necessary for the development of the ER4STEM Framework. Therefore in this evaluation, qualitative data takes primacy.

A semi-structured approach to qualitative data collection was identified as the most suitable. This provided structure where appropriate to provide rigour, flexibility to account for individual research contexts and limited structure to allow for emergent outcomes. Data collection began before the workshop with a Draw-A-Scientist (at work) and throughout the workshop either written observations were recorded or video data was collected of the whole class and/or a focus group. Mid-way through the workshop, students were asked to complete a reflective task and a final reflective task was incorporated into the post-workshop questionnaire. At the end of each sessions the tutors were asked to complete a reflective form. After the final workshop session, a focus group (typically the same focus group in the observations) was invited to take part in a short semi-structured interview. At the end of the workshop artefacts of learning that were created by the students were recorded, this included images of robots that were created, copies of code, structured tasks and students' notes.

Quantitative data was collected through pre- and post-workshop questionnaires, to rapidly survey the opinions of students. The primary purpose of this data was to provide an overview of the background of participants and the outcomes from the workshops from the perspective of the participants. Both quantitative and qualitative have acknowledged limitations but by using a mixed-method approach many of these can be countered.

Table 3 presents an overview of the data collected across the 48 workshops and 1228 students.

Table 3 Overview of data collected

	Number of workshops	Number of participants
Pre-questionnaire	48	1133 (92%)
Post-questionnaire	48	1052 (85%)
Draw-a-Scientist	48	1094 (89%)
Observations	47	n/a
Interviews	35	193 (16%)
Artefacts of Learning	47	n/a
Student Reflections	40	Varies (individual and group)
Tutor Reflections	45	Varies (all or some tutors)

Using the pre-kit (D6.1), evaluation data was collected during all of the 48 workshops. As described in D2.1. Of the 1228 students who participated, 1133 (92%) completed the pre-workshop questionnaire and 1052 (85%) completed the post-workshop questionnaire. This data is used to gain evidence on students' experience, attitudes and assumptions. To complement this, 1094 (89%) completed the Draw-a-Scientist task.

To gain an in-depth understanding of the workshops to inform the development of the framework; observer, teacher and student perspectives were recorded through various instruments. In addition to those already mentioned, 39 of the 48 workshops (81%) were observed using a variety of tools including written observation schedules and video. In all but one of the remaining 9 workshops, photographs provided an alternative snapshot record. To understand the workshop from the perspective of the teacher or tutor, reflections were collected from 45 of the 48 workshop tutors (93%). A sample of participants who attended 35 of the workshops took part in a small-group interview after the workshop. This sample represents over 16% of all participants in year 1. Additionally, 83% of students produced personal or team-based reflections on their experiences. The interviews and reflections, supplement the post-workshop questionnaires, observations and artefacts of the learning process, to provide detailed insight into the learner experience during the workshops.

The evaluation of workshops in project year 1 had two aims: 1) to pilot the evaluation kit (pre-kit) and 2) to collect baseline data. Partners involved in using the pre-kit, produced in D6.1 provided additional feedback on the use and usefulness of the evaluation kit which will be used to inform the development of the final evaluation kit to be used in project years 2 and 3. Feedback from partners was collected during and after workshop implementation on the integration of the evaluation into workshops. This shows that while initial data collection at the start of year 1 was hampered by unfamiliarity, over time the evaluation protocol was refined and became a more integrated part of each workshop, thus improving the quality and quantity of data collected. Lessons learned from this process will be incorporated in the refinement of the final evaluation kit, particularly the introduction of questionnaires differentiated by age (D6.2).

3.3 DATA ANALYSIS

Concurrent, mixed-method data analysis often nests the data analysis of one form of data within another. In this project the focus is on the development of the ER4STEM Framework and therefore the 'how' and 'why' questions are given primacy along with qualitative methods. With a large data set, variety of baseline research questions and range of evaluation criteria, the data analysis was split into 3 levels. While much of the data analysis was concurrent, split between different teams, these levels represent the varying depth of analysis and extent to which they take a post-positivist or interpretivist viewpoint.

Following this section the findings are split into four sections (4-6 below), to provide a feel for the results produced by the four levels of analysis that were undertaken. Following the analysis of the raw data, the next phase of data analysis requires the analysis of the findings in relation to each other and the identification of key recommendations. This follows in sections 7 and 8, which follow the findings.

Rigour

The workshop tutors, most of whom have little or no experience as researchers, acted as participant-researchers, collecting data during their own workshops. This has a certain number of advantages, such as no language barriers, ease of access, control over timings of structured data collection and finding contextually appropriate data collection activities. An example of the latter would be the quick group-by-group discussions held at the start of the second day of the Bulgarian workshop to record each group's reflections on the previous day. Another example was the Maltese 'write a postcard' solution. With this comes certain disadvantages, including variation in the form of the data (for example between the Bulgarian and Maltese reflections the students are addressing different audiences and so would say different things, one was spoken and the other written) and rigour in its collection.

However, unlike typical participant-research, each workshop tutor handed a complete set of data for their workshop over to an experienced data analyst. The process of data analysis was divided between the three academic project partners who had different roles: 1 on quantitative analysis, 2 on qualitative data analysis, with the WP leader also organising the process, ensuring reliability across teams and synthesising the analysis of all partners to develop triangulated findings. An outsider perspective was achieved with no researcher analysing data from their own workshop, to reduce researcher bias. In addition, all partners were available to provide any additional contextual information that was required for the analysis and interpretation of findings.

Level 1: In depth case studies

Case studies provide a way to understand the complexity of anything from an individual's life to a series of events. Case studies explore a phenomenon situated within a bounded real-life context (Yin, 2009), resulting in a rich description of the case. Each case is a tightly bound system. In the case of this project, each workshop is treated as a single case as it is implemented in a consistent location, by a consistent set of tutors, with a consistent group of children, engaging in a consistent task.

Stake (1995) presents three types of case studies; intrinsic, instrumental and collective. Intrinsic case studies are undertaken to understand a case of inherent interest to the researcher. The purpose of

the evaluation is to understand the case rather than to test a hypothesis or build theory, although it does not prohibit this outcome (Stake, 2005). It is also exploratory. Exploratory case studies are used to generate and refine research questions and hypotheses when there is a dearth of existing literature and theory in the area (Yin, 2009). While this type of case study can also be used for piloting, the results of the study may be of substantial interest to the field, identifying and elaborating on key concepts in an otherwise broad field (Yin, 2003). However subsequent studies conducted on the improved understanding provided by the exploratory case cannot incorporate the original exploratory data, thus preventing 'bleed' from the exploratory study (Yin, 2003). Importantly though, this does not prevent comparisons between years, only that the data cannot be combined into a single unit.

The limitation of this approach is that the findings are not generalizable beyond the bounds of the case study. However a multiple case study does not necessarily address this issue either. Although the same workshop may be implemented multiple times, there can be small but significant differences in the tutors and location which may have an impact. Additionally, lessons learnt from a previous workshop may be applied, thus changing the workshop and perhaps more importantly the workshops are being implemented with a different group of children. So while a cross-case analysis is possible, in subsequent phases of analysis, each case needs to be analysed as a single case study first. In years 2 and 3 of the project a cross-case and between-case analysis will be adopted for comparison to previous years.

Ideally case studies contain a wide range of data, to counter concerns about reliability and validity, through triangulation. As a pilot of the evaluation pre-kit and administered by often inexperienced workshop tutors, there can be an expectation that there will be uncollected or unusable data sets. However, as shown in Table 3, almost all workshops had multiple data sets collected and many had full data sets collected. Therefore there were a variety of cases to choose from. Those with full data sets were analysed in the following way:

- Familiarisation:
 - Begin by familiarising self with activity plan and then workshop information for more specifics, querying tutors as necessary.
 - Review data from the workshop in chronological order:
 - Workshop video & observations
 - Teacher and student reflections
 - Interviews
 - Post-questionnaire
- Analysis Phase 1:
 - Begin with the activity plan– evaluating it through a pedagogic lens.
 - Identify important contextual information from the activity plan and workshop information.
 - Structured document analysis – looking for key information.
 - Interviews
 - Open coding
 - Structured analysis
 - Student reflections
 - Open coding of reflection at mid-point and reflective questions in the post-questionnaire.
 - Structured analysis
 - Teacher reflections
 - Open coding

- Structured analysis
- Pre- and post-questionnaires
 - Quantitative analysis
 - Frequencies. This sample is too small for statistical analysis.
 - Qualitative analysis
 - Open coding of open questions.
 - Structured analysis
 - Comparative analysis.
 - Identification of potential outliers
- Observations
 - First create a descriptive account highlighting interesting events, room layout, teaching time vs student activity time and movement in the room.
 - Return to interesting events to unpick the actions.
 - Structured analysis
- Analysis Phase 2:
 - Triangulation
- Analysis Phase 3:
 - Counter evidence
- Analysis Phase 4:
 - Participant tracking
- Member checking

In each case, the activity plan was analysed through a pedagogic lens. This means that it was reviewed from the perspective of a teacher who would want to implement this activity with a group of students, to identify key information for the implementation and what was missing, to inform the activity plan and framework. This also informs the evaluation by showing what the workshop organisers are explicitly aware of, as it is very difficult to share tacit knowledge. Both should be visible in the video data. It will also provide opportunities for clarification with workshop organisers, allowing them to make explicit some of their implicit assumptions and actions which should improve their reporting and planning of future workshops. This can be evaluated in future years, using this data as a baseline. This analysis goes on to inform the structured analysis of other data sets, for example the videos are analysed for evidence of the learning outcomes, activities described and classroom orchestration.

Interviews and reflections were openly coded using the constant comparative approach. Within individual cases some tentative categories emerged which were used to inform the structured analysis of other data sets. The pre and post-questionnaire data was analysed by tabulating results for each quantitative question and the open coding of qualitative data. Again, the emerging findings from these results informed the structured analysis of other data sets. Observational data was treated in several ways. Where there was only video, a descriptive account was first written with notes/memos on 'interesting moments' or potentially 'critical episodes'. These were later returned to and the action was described in more detail, before being analysed.

As can be seen from the above description, although the data analysis process appears to be linear, it requires the researcher to return to earlier sets of data with a fresh eye to consider a feature which has emerged from another data set.

Following this first phase of in depth data analysis, the data is triangulated and then examples of counter evidence are sought. Triangulation seeks to provide validity to the findings from any one data set by using the findings of others to confirm or refute. Counter evidence allows us to identify

instances where something may not occur as expected, for example in a case study where all students give the workshop 5 out of 5 stars, except for one child who gives it 2. While this does not refute the finding that the students enjoyed the workshop, it does point to a potentially interesting area for analysis, that will inform the Framework by allowing us to consider “What works for whom, when, how and why” by also understanding when things do not work. Therefore the fourth phase of analysis ‘participant tracking’ is used to gain a fine grained understanding of that participant’s experience during the workshop and how it varied to the norm.

Finally there is a process of member checking, where the interpretation of the data is checked with members of the workshop. In these cases only the tutors were available to comment. This involved queries from the researcher to members and sharing the report with members for comment. Where members of the case disagreed with the analysis, it was returned to and reconsidered.

Level 2: Single country analysis

In this analysis, the data from a single country is treated as part of a multiple case study, with each workshop a single case. A descriptive qualitative analysis provides information on the characteristics and properties of the phenomenon under investigation and allows the researchers to identify areas for further, future investigation, much like an exploratory case study. Unlike an in-depth case study which is fully open and at times directed by emergent findings, the country analysis focuses on specific research areas, whilst remaining open to emergent findings. The single country analysis focused on the evaluation criteria:

- Learner engagement
- Changing & sustaining attitudes to STEM
- Connecting STEM to society
- Creativity
- Collaborative working
- Entrepreneurial activity
- Questions for using specific tools
- Evaluate teacher use of ER repository
- What works, for whom and in what circumstances?
- Plans for further development of activities.

While these were not the focus of the analysis in Year 1, this analysis provided an opportunity to evaluate the pre-kit (D6.1) in relation to the Year 1 pilot and assess whether it would be fit for purpose in Year 2.

The first stage was to collect and prepare all qualitative data from the country. The audio files of all interviews were transcribed and the qualitative responses from the pre and post questionnaires were collated. Where video was available, the video files of the focus groups were examined throughout and some parts of them were chosen to be transcribed. These were selected on the basis that they clearly depicted the activity that was going on or the interaction between the students. Finally the photos and the text files with students’ and tutor’s reflections between the sessions were used in the analysis.

The data were then mapped, when that was possible, having as a key the students’ id in order to have a complete data set for each student. Then the data were coded according to the categories identified *a priori* based on the 10 evaluation criteria. These clusters contained specific answers to

open questions of the questionnaires or/and specific critical episodes of the transcripts which are dialogues or phrases of the students that indicate important terms in relation to the evaluation criteria.

Level 3: Single data set

The third level of analysis, took one data set from all countries to review the activities of all partners in relation to the baseline questions. Due to the focus on the baseline question and breadth (all countries) of this analysis, the activity plans, draw a scientist and quantitative questionnaire data were chosen as the most comparable and complete data sets.

Activity plans were analysed as a single set to inform the development of the Activity Plan (WP4). Importantly they were analysed without knowledge of how the plans were actioned during the workshop, so as not to bias the evaluation. Additionally they were analysed by someone who did not design the workshops, so that an unbiased outside perspective could be taken. Analysis of the activity plans began with the pedagogic evaluation of the activity plans, as reported in D4.1. This ensured familiarity with the data before focusing on answering the baseline questions. This section of the report presents the reflective analysis of the activity plans from all partner, before responding to the individual baseline questions.

The pre and post-workshop questionnaires were cleaned before analysis. This included the removal of participants who had only completed one of the two questionnaires, so that the data sets were comparable. Following the tabulation of frequencies of Likert scale questions, the mean and standard deviation were calculated. The analysis then focused on answering the baseline questions and identifying any unexpected results.

The final data set to be included in this analysis is the Draw-A-Scientist-Test, which was not included in earlier analyses as it provided no information about the workshops themselves. What this data does tell us about is the conscious and unconscious biases and stereotypes held by children about scientists. While this information can be used to help us understand some of the observed behaviours, its real value lies in clarifying the starting point in terms of assumptions that students have and why they are challenging to address.

The analysis of the Draw-A-Scientist data takes an open coding approach to all items observable within a picture, categorizing them as part of the scientist's appearance, as objects within the room, or 'other'. The other category contains all non-physical objects made physical within the drawing, for example a light-bulb which appears to be switched on above the head of a scientist typically indicates an idea. Words such as "explosion" or "boom" would also be included in this category. Unlike the traditional Draw-A-Scientists-Task, students were asked to add words to their drawing explaining what was happening in their picture. The majority of students labelled objects within the picture making them easier to identify. Those who wrote more typically wrote one or two short sentences rather than length prose. These sentences were analysed separately. Through a constant comparative analysis approach was applied to both visual and written data.

4 FINDINGS OF CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

This section presents the findings of 2 case studies. These are selected as they include full data sets; represent two different countries; include workshops which are and are not aligned to the curriculum.

For each country the findings are presented by data set, before a within-workshop discussion of the findings which draws out further triangulation, counter evidence and participant tracking across data sets.

4.1 BULGARIA

Findings

CONTEXT AND ACTIVITY PLAN:

In this case we are looking at a 'Practical Robotics Workshop' in Bulgaria, in which the primary domain is robotics. This activity plan was designed for children aged 9-10 with no prior knowledge of robotics or programming, by ESI-CEE, a technical company. The subject related objectives were:

- To learn the key robotics elements
- To construct a robot
- To develop a visual programme to control the robot
- To develop the creative thinking skills needed to find different applications of robotics in other fields.

Further objectives identified relate to Arduino controllers, motor drivers, ultrasonic sensors, teamwork skills, creative thinking, presenting results, problem solving, formulating and expressing ideas, listening skills, problem solving and decision making within a team. However it is clear that these are not objectives as defined by educationalists, as they do not define the goal of the workshop in terms of demonstrable skills or knowledge that will be acquired by students. For example, it is unclear whether students will be taught how to present results, whether they will be expected to develop their listening skills or demonstrate their problem solving skills.

This highlights an area for development through the Framework and Activity Plan to provide a guide for the construction of measurable objectives, which can clearly be implemented, by those who are not experienced practitioners. This may include a set of skills for workshop designers to draw from with examples of suitable objectives for each skill. In the revised Activity Plan, examples are now given which provides a starting point for the second year of the project. However it would not be possible, nor would it be desirable, to present these in a structured model of progression as these are skills which take time to develop, need to be returned to and practiced. Similarly it would not be possible to associate these with particular age groups as each countries' educational system will introduce these skills at different points, if at all.

Each team of 3-4 students was provided with a standard robotics kit developed by ESI CEE. The children were aged between 9 and 10 years old and participated in two 4 hour sessions on different days. On the first day 28 students participated and on the second 24. The change in participation is not unexpected. Participation in workshops which are implemented over more than one day within a standard school day are likely to be affected from typical school absence. Absence was equally distributed across genders. There were no children known to have additional learning needs.

The activity plan allowed for one instructor per 3 teams, so in this case there were 3 instructors available during the workshop. In total there were 7 teams which were formed by the students themselves, allowing them to choose who they worked with. On day 1 all teams were comprised of 4 members. Absence had limited impact on groups with four of the groups losing 1 member each. Of

the 7 teams, 2 were mixed-gender groups, the focus group (2 male, 2 female) and one group which lost a female member on the second day (1 male, 3 female on day 1).

There were no predefined roles for members of the team but the activity plan also states that the students would be encouraged to change roles between team leader, programmer, robot developer and presenter. From this limited information it is unclear to what extent the children would be presented with these roles, expected to remain within them or could freely move between tasks even if it was outside their 'official' role. This highlights a potential area for development in educational robotics activities. Many studies reported in the literature state that participants worked in teams, but the orchestration of those teams is rarely discussed. As shown in this example, describing the organisation of teams is complex. However it is essential if 'what works' is to be identified and shared with researchers and practitioners. Therefore there is a need to return to the research literature on group work and explore how the Framework could scaffold the description of the social orchestration of team work within the Activity Plans. This may be achieved by providing different examples which can easily be modified to suit specific contexts. Further analysis of Year 1 data along with the ongoing data collection and analysis in Year 2 of the project will be able to provide evidence to support and develop different models of team work within the context of educational robotics activities.

The teaching and learning approaches, along with the sequence and description of activities is limited in the first version of the activity plan, which has since been updated. The activity plan for this workshop identified potential misconceptions and cognitive conflicts but provides no rationale or planned actions to mitigate these. A follow-up conversation with the team who ran the workshop revealed uncertainty as to why there was the anticipated preconception/misconception of students that "competing is the main goal". The main reason was due to past experience of running similar workshops, although they were unsure as to why students would be competitive. One suggestion was that younger students in Bulgaria are not familiar with team work and so resort to competitive behaviours. While competitive behaviours can be positive, there can also be negative outcomes including anger, tears, recklessness and verbal abuse, creating a negative environment for both students and tutors, as described by one team member. Interestingly they reported that they do have an approach to mitigate the effects of this, however this was not documented in the activity plan.

From the activity plan it is difficult to know how each activity would be implemented. For example, without seeing the PowerPoint presentation materials and the video of the first day, it would be impossible for another teacher or workshop leader to implement the activities described. Equally, it is unclear what the process is through which the "basic concepts of robotics are thought through and discussed", whether they are introduced by the teacher, brainstormed by the students, discussed as a whole class or within small groups. Similarly in the second part of the sequence "student teams program the robot to execute simple tasks", however it is unclear as to whether these tasks are provided by the tutors; whether students, having completed some introductory tasks, go on to create their own tasks; or whether students develop their own tasks from the beginning. This is essential knowledge which needs to be shared in the activity plan and accompanying materials as it relates closely to the objectives identified at the beginning of the activity plan. This sequence of activities also does not demonstrate how the social and action related objectives, or the argumentation and fostering maker culture objectives are realised.

An excellent example of what would be valuable in the activity plan is provided in the supplementary lesson materials provided by the project partner as part of the evaluation data. This document

provides a brief overview of the programming language Scratch, followed by a section entitled ‘What we do’.

We prepare in advance a little program divided in blocks, designed to control the tanks and its motors and sensors. Children work with this file as their job is to pull out different blocks and give them the necessary values to perform certain tasks.

For instance, one of the tasks is to make the tank turn left – to make this they have to think for themselves which motor should be running and which one not in order for the tank to go left. To do this, they have to assign the respective values to each motor after choosing the right blocks for the task and dropping them in the programming field. They could change those by assigning different values, they can make sequences and cycles with those actions.

What is usually done is we show them how to make the tank go forwards and how to program the ultrasonic sensor, after which we leave them to explore themselves how they could make the tank go in the other directions and provide support if needed. We try to encourage them to think for themselves

This provides a very clear synopsis of the activity from both teacher and student perspectives in the first paragraph and is followed by a specific example. The final paragraph explains more of the orchestration. This document was written after the activity plan at the request of the WP6 lead, which suggests that with more experience of communicating workshop activities to others, partners may become more aware of the types of information that are needed by others and so activity plans may be more detailed.

Overall we can see that while it covers many aspects of the planned workshop, the Activity Plan at this stage in development does not support the development of objectives by non-specialists, or the alignment of these objectives with the sequence of activities. It is also unclear as to how a practitioner or researcher could assess whether their activity had been successful. In the ER4STEM project this is achieved through a number of tools, including video observations, student and teacher reflections and student interviews. However if educational robotics are to be used in mainstream classrooms, beyond the research, teachers themselves need to be able to assess the achievement of their learners in relation to the goals. With broad aims such as “construct a robot” in this workshop, it is easy for a teacher/tutor to simply observe whether a team has achieved this or not. However it may be more difficult to show that students have “learned the key robotics elements”.

Since this workshop was implemented the Activity Plan has been revised and provides a new template for Year 2 of the project, which is detailed in D4.1. The analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of the activity plans as a whole, along with the detailed analysis of individual cases from Year 1 in this report will provide valuable baseline data with which to measure improvement or deterioration in the presentation of workshops in the Activity Plans.

OBSERVATIONS

The video data provides a clear view on the action that occurred at different points during the workshop. The workshop takes place in a computer room, in which desktop computers are on

benches around the three sides of the room. For the purposes of this research the front of the room is considered to be the one side without computers, where the tutors typically stand. At the back of the room is a screen on the wall which is often used to demonstrate and give instructions. Portable tables are placed along each of the three sides at regular intervals pointing into the room, allowing two children to sit each side. Each table has a shelf and appears to be designed to be sat at only on one side. In this report, selected 'interesting moments' are presented and discussed.

At the end of the first session the children are introduced to the NAO robot. For the majority of the time the adults control and interact with the robot. However when the robot is exploring its environment, the children create a natural barrier and a few of them wave at it, causing it to sense an obstruction and change direction. This and other behaviours such as lying on the floor and getting up are enjoyed by the children with them applauding and positioning themselves closer and closer. However there is less visually obvious enjoyment when NAO is presenting monologues in English. This may be because this is a second language the children are learning and they do not understand. Additionally there is no movement by NAO and no interaction with its environment.

The focus group, group 1, consists of two boys and two girls who sit on opposite sides of the table to each other in single-gender pairs. In session 2, the boys appear to be the most engaged with the activity, with 1 preparing to place the robot on the obstacle course and the other stood by him, whilst 1 girl is at the computer ready to start the robot when instructed and the other is sat watching. During testing the track comes off the robot and the boys return to the desk with the robot and attempt to fix it, neither of the girls are involved and appear to be drawing on some paper. When they return to test the robot again, it is the boys who go to the testing area and the girls remain at the desk. At this point it appears that interacting with the robot appears to be a boy's job, whilst the girls are only able to watch.

Later we see that most of the class have left for a break, including the two boys from group 1 but the two girls have remained, as have two girls from another group. The group 1 girls are now sitting where the boys were. Whilst one edits the code, the other is looking at the screen, pointing and making suggestions. The girl who is not at the computer goes to pick up the robot, which the male tutor takes from her and repairs (the track has fallen off again). She watches him whilst first girl looks at computer screen and types.

There is some interaction between this group and the other group of girls in the room before the rest of the class returns. The boys return to the table and the girl at the computer starts explaining what they did in the break and executes the programme so they the boys can see what the girls have done. There is some reassertion of their original position as the boys move round to where the girls are sat and, without being told, the girls move from their seat with some apparent reluctance. Shortly after this there appears to be a disagreement within the group, on which one of the tutors was contacted for clarification. She stated that whilst she couldn't hear what they were saying on the video, having been in the room she remembered that during this episode when they returned to the room one of the boys was surprised by how much the girls had done, including things he didn't know how to do. Later when the argument occurred it appears to be because the girls had programmed the robot to say they were its best friends and the boys were not happy about this.

In relation to the activities that they had to complete, as the full workshop was not filmed, it is unclear from the observations and activity plan how much of the programme they wrote themselves, whether they were given a half-baked solution or a blank canvas.

STUDENT REFLECTIONS

At the beginning of the second session, each team took part in a short, informal discussion with one of the tutors, to reflect on what they had done so far. Standardised questions were asked and from the teams' responses it is clear that the construction of the robot was both the biggest challenge and the greatest achievement for each team. The importance of experiencing success during the workshops is commented on by one of the tutors in their reflections, which are discussed below. At this point in the workshop they had learned not only how to build a robot but also the importance of attention to detail in the construction of the robot.

For some teams, while robot construction was still the biggest challenge, they identified team work as their greatest achievement at this point in the workshop. This included working together and more specifically for one group developing a positive working relationship through which they came to understand that "it is not always important to be the boss". This comment came from group 5 which had one absent member that day but before this was made up of 3 girls and 1 boy.

At the end of the workshop the reflection was built into the questionnaire through three open questions: What have you learned about yourself? What have you learned about working with other people? What have you learned about working with robots? From their responses it is clear that they have increased their sense of self-efficacy through the workshop, particularly in relation to creating and programming robots. They identified benefits of working in a team such as helping each other and enjoyment, whilst recognising that they had learned to listen to, help and respect others. When considering what they had learned about working with robots, students mostly referred to it being fun, difficult and interesting, with some reference to the construction and programming of the robot. This would be in line with the concept of robots supporting meaningful learning through 'hard fun', a concept which is raised in the more detailed analysis of the questionnaire responses below.

TUTOR REFLECTIONS

Following each of the workshops, tutors were asked to complete a reflection on the day. Two tutors completed a reflection for the first session and three for the second session. Their reflections highlight a number of personal observations throughout the workshop and helps to reveal some of their actions, and what they have learnt from the workshop themselves.

One important event that related to student disengagement and teamwork was commented on, which relates to the group who were interviewed and so this provides valuable contextual information. It is interesting to note that the reporting of this activity highlights gender stereotypes in different forms. On day 1 the female tutor noted that at times the girls in Group 1, which was comprised of two girls and two boys, were excluded from the activity by the boys, with one of the girls going to her to say "that the boys do not allow them (the girls) to work". The tutor goes on to note that while generally friendly, the boys "did make some sexist remarks and left the girls behind", suggesting that this may be because the boys "didn't have the chance to see their abilities and their knowledge / skills in the field". The male tutor noted that "two girls were isolated by two boys in the same team". He then "talked to the group and convinced them that the girls should be included". This is an interesting incident which requires further exploration by analysing those students' individual questionnaire responses, the team's reflection, their interview and the video data. However it goes beyond the scope of baseline data analysis, so it will be examined in the following round of data analysis in more depth.

On the second day more students from different groups were noted not to be engaging but only for a short period of time. One reason suggested for this was leadership conflict. This raises questions about the orchestration of the teams at the beginning of the workshop, their past experiences of teamwork and the nature of the activities. Unfortunately there is insufficient information in the activity plan to explore this in any significant detail. It also raises a need for more information gathering about students' experiences of teamwork before and after the workshop.

Overall the tutors noted that the students "managed their conflict themselves and were good at it", which was not anticipated in the activity plan.

Due to their speed, there was additional time for demonstrating and interacting with the NAO robot with questions and answers, including a discussion on the application of and different types of robots. This had not previously been achieved in other workshops and may account for the knowledge and ideas expressed by the students who participated in the interview which demonstrate achievement of the subject related objectives. The tutor also noted the value of this additional discussion and listed aspects of it in the section of the reflection form which asked them for three things that they would change next time. This suggests that following this experience, this tutor believes that opportunities for discussion may be more valuable for learning in this context than previously considered.

Tutors noted that students developed their creative thinking skills, programmed robots and generally were curious and interested throughout the workshop, finding the activities fun. However it was also noted that students had a need for validation.

From their reflections, the tutors took an active role in supporting and monitoring teams throughout the workshop. Students were observed to have a positive sense of self-efficacy from beginning to end, which supported an exploratory approach to learning. They were often fast at their work but would often make mistakes which resulted in a need for tutors to support them.

From the reflections on the second session, it is clear that the activities required a lot of tutor support and "it was difficult to monitor everybody's work". While the post-questionnaire suggests that students found the tasks difficult but fun, suggesting 'hard fun' considered positive, it raises questions about the level of difficulty (was it too difficult) and the potential of using other supports to scaffold learning. While students were provided with a visual guide for the construction of the robot on the first day, could similar supports be provided on the second? Is there something particular about the tasks or the pedagogical approach which would preclude their use? Unfortunately it is unclear from the activity plan and may be a point for consideration in the development of the Framework and Activity Plan.

Overall evidence from the reflection raises questions about whether robotics activities such as this could be undertaken in a typical classroom setting where there is only one teacher. What supports would the teacher need to put in place to allow them to achieve the successful implementation of this activity? One suggestion raised by a tutor which both informal workshop leaders and classroom teachers should consider is the role of the tutor, with clear distribution of roles where there are multiple tutors available.

INTERVIEWS

Following the final workshop, one team was invited to participate in a short interview (11 minutes) about their experiences during the workshop. Both open and structured analysis of the interview was undertaken and the results are presented here.

The interview began by asking the students to describe what they had done during the workshop and what they had liked most. It was clear that they had enjoyed the workshop with reference made to building and programming robots, as well as studying science and maths. They demonstrated a sense of self-efficacy around the construction and programming of robots, indicating that they learned the importance of perseverance when something didn't work.

While they liked working in a team they agree that it was difficult at times. When asked how they worked as a team the students stated that:

C2 (male): Everybody took every part of the robot and waited afterwards for the others.

C4 (female): When someone said that they would like to try something or do something, we tried to listen and give each other turns... and we gradually built it

This excerpt demonstrates that they worked together and displayed listening and co-operation skills. However it also highlights that they had a distributed rather than collaborative approach to working.

When asked why they thought team work was important they referenced the increased speed at which they could achieve things, correcting errors and asking for help from each other. However there was little to suggest that they learned from each other, instead, students described doing things for others, rather than showing them how.

When asked to describe what makes a good scientist, the actions and knowledge of scientists were the main focus of children's accounts. They identified the study of mathematics and general science with the creation of robots and discovery of new things as activities that scientists are involved in, as well as the need for experience and perseverance.

There were clear influences from popular media. Within their descriptions it is clear that there are fantasy or fictional elements which would be commonly associated with the portrayal of scientists in popular media, for this age group (9-10), most likely cartoons, children's programmes or films. Both male and female students describe "a good scientist" as one who is smart and knows what they are doing, by comparison to a bad scientist who is very smart but could do a lot of evil and "if he doesn't know what he does, he'll make something and when he tries to switch it on...it will explode." There is of course the possibility that students have interpreted the question of what makes a scientist good, in relation to notions of good and evil, which would similarly relate to the portrayal of good and evil scientists. Analysis of the same students' draw-a-scientist pictures and writing supports the hypothesis that they are influenced by popular media, however this data also suggests that this may be gendered, with the female students drawing more realistic pictures of scientists at work.

Throughout the interview it is clear that students have developed a conceptual relationship between science and robotics. They view robots as helpful tools or partners within their own future work environments and while their descriptions of scientists tended towards popular media stereotypes, the students were able to demonstrate on several occasions throughout the interview that they had a generally realistic view of what robots are and how they work.

While stereotypical views of scientists are held by children of this age, an interesting point to note from the interviews is that perseverance was an attribute of scientists ascribed by the interview participants, who went on to mention the importance of perseverance when asked to describe what they would tell others about their experience during the workshop. This had not previously been mentioned in the draw-a-scientist activity and appears to have been something that they have learnt or grown to appreciate over the course of the workshop.

There was some reference to 9 of the 14 objectives outlined in the activity plan. Three of those were listed under technology use. There are a number of potential reasons for this. The students may not have been taught or may not have remembered the technology that they were using. If either of these is the case it is worth considering whether these are relevant objectives.

The other two were presenting results and problem solving. It is unclear from the interview that students engaged with these but there is evidence from the questionnaire to suggest that they were aware of engaging in problem solving. However there is no clarity on the presentation of results and it is unclear from the activity plan when there might have been an opportunity for this.

The comments made by students suggest that all subject related objectives were engaged with, although it is unclear what was learned. An understanding of the key robotics elements is apparent and they have developed some ideas for the application of robotics in different fields, as demonstrated by their talk of using robots to assist them in different jobs. However, other than mentioning that they had constructed a robot, there was no explicit awareness of what they had learnt through the process. This is similarly true for the programming of the robot, although there is an emerging sense of self-efficacy in this area.

Students were able to demonstrate in the interview that they were able to formulate and express ideas and engage in creative thinking and it is most likely that the creative thought session that morning and later discussions that were available during the NAO activity supported this.

Through the open coding in advance of the structured analysis it was clear that students had engaged with teamwork and developed an awareness of listening as part of this. However, as previously highlighted, there are questions about whether students simply distributed the work between them or actually collaborated as a team.

QUESTIONNAIRE

The pre- and post-workshop provide useful background information about students and provide a snapshot of their perceptions of the workshop. In this case, 28 students completed the pre-workshop questionnaire and 24 completed the post-workshop questionnaire, due to natural attrition. It should be noted that not all responses reported in the tables below add up to the number of respondents for each questionnaire as some children did not answer some questions. However the overall response for each item was high.

Between the pre- and post-workshop questionnaires the majority of children's job aspirations remained constant and these are congruent with the literature on aspiration for this age group. However it is worth noting that 3 children (1 girl, 2 boys) changed their answer in the post-questionnaire from cook, seamstress and captain, to scientist. At this point it is not possible to draw any conclusions from this result, however it suggests that by engaging in the workshop students may consider STEM careers. This trend is corroborated in the post-questionnaire in which 22 students

stated that they were now more interested in studying science and 23 were more interested in learning how things work.

While 12 of the 28 students reported that they had created robots, the majority of these appear to be Lego models. This highlights a lack of knowledge about what a robot is before the workshop. Fewer students stated that they had experience of programming and there was limited evidence to suggest that they understood what was meant by programming. Therefore, for the purpose of this analysis, this group of children are considered to have little or no knowledge of programming or robotics.

The pre-questionnaire was designed to provide baseline data on each student, to characterise the individual case; for comparison across cases and between countries; and to identify students whose data would be particularly interesting to analyse in depth.

Of the 28 students that completed the pre-workshop questionnaire, 8 identified STEM subjects as their favourite, with reasons including that it is interesting, fun and easy. While one student noted that they liked mathematics because they love solving problems, another was more instrumental, stating that they got their highest grades in this subject.

9 students identified STEM subjects as the ones that they liked the least, with the difficulty of these subjects the main reason. However they have an awareness that science is important, as all students agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that it is important to learn about science (Table 4).

Table 4 Pre-questionnaire Likert responses to statements about themselves.

Statement	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
I like using computers	28	0	0
I know a lot about robots	11	7	9
I learn best with other people	25	0	3
I like science	19	7	2
I like maths	19	3	5
I like working on my own	9	6	13
I like working in teams	27	1	0
I like trying to solve difficult problems	23	4	0
I need help solving problems	19	0	9
I am good at solving problems	21	4	1
I want to understand more about mechanical things	25	2	1
I want to solve problems that can help people	26	2	0
I prefer tasks that only have one correct answer	19	3	4
I like to keep working on a project until it is perfect	23	4	0
I like it when I can solve problems quickly	22	4	0
I think it is important to learn about science	28	0	0
I like learning about how things work	25	3	1

To understand students' perceptions of maths and science, a series of statements were responded to on a Likert-scale (reported in Table 5 and Table 6 respectively), followed by a question as to whether the students would like to study maths and science when they are older. In this case, 17 students stated that they would like to study maths when they are older and 20 said that they would like to study science.

Table 5 Pre-questionnaire Likert responses to statements about maths.

Statement	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
In general I find maths easy	21	2	5
Maths lessons are boring	9	4	14
We have fun in maths lessons	13	9	6
Maths is important for the job I want to do	24	2	2
My teacher thinks I am good at maths	23	2	2
I get good grades in maths	18	7	1
I have to work on my own in maths	21	1	4
Maths is the most interesting subject in school	17	3	5
Maths is important to learn	27	0	1

Table 6 Pre-questionnaire Likert responses to statements about science.

Statement	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
Science is the most interesting subject in school	17	3	8
In general I find science easy	20	6	2
Science lessons are boring	7	6	14
We have fun in science lessons	19	6	2
Science is important for the job I want to do	19	2	5
My teacher thinks I am good at science	25	2	1
I have to work on my own in science	10	8	8
I think science is difficult	12	8	7
I get good grades in science	18	6	3
Most of the student in my class are good at science	20	6	2

Reviewing the Likert-scale responses to statements on maths and science, we see that these students have a generally positive attitude and sense of self-efficacy towards both subjects, which mirrors their intention to continue studying these subjects. However there are a few important points to draw from this data. While they generally report having more fun in science lessons, students believe that maths is more important for the job that they want in the future, although more students reported a desire to study science when they are older than maths.

Another notable difference between the children's perceptions of maths and science is their reported self-efficacy in terms of ease or difficulty of the subject. While most find maths easy, the results are less clear for science. Yet in the yes/no questions asked in the post-questionnaire in which 16 students reported that they thought they were good at maths, 21 reported that they were good at science. There is a similar distribution of responses to the question about their attainment in both subjects. Finally, the most striking difference between science and maths lessons is that students report working on their own more in maths than in science. This is considered in the discussion under the heading of teamwork.

After the workshop a second questionnaire was distributed, which aimed to assess the impact of the workshop.

Table 7 shows the responses of the children to the problems which they had to solve during the workshop. Whilst the majority of students perceived the problems to be difficult, all students reported that they were interesting and fun. This suggests that the problems were both appropriate and engaging for the age, ability and experience of the students, aligning with Papert's concept of "hard fun" (Papert, n.d., <http://www.papert.org/articles/HardFun.html>) necessary for learning. Similarly robots appear to be a 'hard fun' tool for learning (Table 8). This is supported by 23 of the students stating that they would like to try to solve more challenges like the ones in the workshop.

Table 7 Post-questionnaire Likert responses to the workshop problems

The problems we had to solve were...	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
Interesting	24	0	0
Difficult	4	5	15
Fun	24	0	0

Table 8 Post-questionnaire perceptions of working with robots

Working with robots was...	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
Interesting	24	0	0
Difficult	4	3	17
Fun	24	0	0

When asked what existing knowledge they had used, 19 students mentioned science, 22 mentioned technology, 8 art, 19 mentioned their knowledge of how things work and 16 mentioned maths. When asked what they had learned about, 17 mentioned science, 22 technology, 7 art, 21 mentioned their knowledge of how things work and 12 mentioned maths. The similarity in these numbers suggests that students may have not realised the difference in these questions, and this assertion is supported by an analysis on the individual student level. This suggests that this part of the post-questionnaire needs to be reconsidered as it may not be measuring what it was intended to measure.

Table 9 presents an overview of students' responses to statements about what they did during the workshop. These statements cover the workshop activities, students own actions, teamwork and resilience.

Table 9 Post-questionnaire Likert responses to statements about the workshop

During the workshop ...	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
I identified a problem to solve	10	6	8
I worked on something that I was interested in	23	1	0
I tried to solve an important problem	12	5	7
I worked as part of a team	23	0	0
I worked on my own	2	0	22
I helped design a robot	20	3	0
I helped create a robot	23	0	1
I helped programme a robot	22	1	0
I was able to choose what I wanted to do	19	4	1

I feel that other people did not listen to me	6	6	12
I did most of the work	5	8	10
I was encouraged by my team	21	3	0
I worked hard	21	2	1
I was bored	3	1	19
I liked sharing what I had done with other people	21	2	1
I helped someone	19	2	1
I gave up too quickly	4	0	20

All students reported that they believed that they were good at working in a team and that they would like to build robots to solve problems in the future. 23 reported that they would like to use robots to learn in the future and 22 reported that they would like to learn more about programming. 20 stated that they knew how important robots can be to solve important problems. 16 reported that they understood how important maths is, whilst 23 reported the same for science.

Overall the students enjoyed the workshop, with 23 stating that they would like to do more activities like this one, whilst all students rated the experience as 5 out of 5. The reasons they gave for this were collected through an open response question, which revealed that they found it interesting and enjoyable. Students referred to the positive presence of the tutors, which is an important consideration with regards to ‘wow’ factor and application by mainstream classroom teachers. Students also liked working with friends and learning about robots, science and maths, and returning to the theme of hard fun, one student stated that they had given the workshop 5 stars because “it was fun and difficult”.

Discussion

In this section, three emerging themes from the data are discussed in further detail. These have been selected as they were common across data sets and therefore present a stronger base from which to draw some initial conclusions, based only on this case study.

TEAMWORK

Although there were concerns about students’ ability to work in teams, one of the differences reported in the pre-questionnaire between science and maths lessons is that students report working on their own more in maths than in science, with only 10 students that they work on their own in science. This suggests that there is some paired, group or team work in science lessons at this school. Correspondence with one of the workshop tutors suggested that this concern was from past experience of other workshops. This tutor suggested that there is a lack of team work in Bulgarian schools at younger ages. However this data casts some doubt on this assertion and highlights this as an area for further consideration throughout the ER4STEM project evaluation.

Whilst the majority of students agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that working in a team was fun and interesting (Table 10), only 15 disagreed or strongly disagreed that it was difficult. It is worth noting that 3 agreed or strongly agreed that it was difficult to work in a team, with 6 offering no opinion either way. Only one of the students in the focus group who were known to have difficulties based on the tutor reflections neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. The other three strongly disagreed that it was difficult to work in a team. This suggests that having been a

dysfunctional team at the beginning of the workshop, the tutor involvement and subsequent work that they did, left them with a positive impression of group work.

Table 10 Post-questionnaire perceptions of working in a team

Working in a team was...	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
Interesting	23	0	1
Difficult	3	6	15
Fun	23	0	1

The three who agreed that working in a team was difficult were all girls, with one stating that they had worked on their own. However they also agreed that working in a team was both interesting and fun, suggesting that this is not a simple dislike of team work. One student stated that she felt that the other students in her team did not listen to her and she did most of the work but was also bored. In response to the reflective question ‘what have you learned about yourself’, she stated that she had learned that she could do it herself. It is also worth noting that the three girls were distributed across two all-female groups. It is not possible to generate any conclusions from these findings, however they do highlight areas for wider analysis across students who participate in this workshop as well as across workshops and will be an area for follow-up analysis.

From Table 9 presented earlier, it is clear that while students worked as part of a team, the teams were not always fully functional, with students reporting that they were not listened to, feeling that they did most of the work. The focus group shows that the boys did not meaningfully collaborate with the girls, within the pair of girls and pair of boys there was collaboration. Also, there is evidence to suggest that collaboration between the two genders increased once popular stereotypes that the boys held had been successfully challenged by the girls. However there were also many positive aspects that students experienced from team work, particularly the support they gave and gained.

EVIDENCE OF LEARNING

This section explores each of the learning objectives identified in the activity and presents evidence on whether students engaged with this objective and whether they achieved it. In some cases this is complicated due to skills or objects listed rather than clear objectives and so in these instances relevant data is discussed from the perspectives of learner engagement and knowledge acquisition.

Learn the key robotics elements:

The pre-questionnaire highlights a limited understanding of what a robot is before the workshop, while in the interview students demonstrated an understanding of the key features of a robot and how it can be distinguished from a machine.

Construct a robot:

Throughout the data there is clear evidence that students constructed a robot but it is unclear what they learned from this process. However one student in the interview did make the following comment which illustrates a developing understanding of electronics:

“you have to know which cable serves for what. Because if you have a cable for turning on, it will look in one way, if you have a cable for... for example for turning on lights, it will look in another way”

This suggests that some learning has occurred but what and how explicit this knowledge is and how transferable it is, is unclear.

Develop a visual programme to control the robot:

Again, it is clear throughout that the students programmed the robot using the visual language Scratch and demonstrated a strong sense of self-efficacy. However it is again unclear what they learnt beyond this. It is also unclear from the observations and activity plan how much of this programme they wrote themselves; whether they were given a half-baked solution or a blank canvas.

Develop the creative thinking skills needed to find different applications of robotics in other fields:

The second session provided students with an introduction to creative thinking and at the end of the session they were provided with an extended opportunity to ask questions and discuss ideas. Additionally it is clear from the interviews that the students were able to think of different applications of robots. It is difficult to conclude that the former was due to the latter but it may have stimulated some of the ideas that were shared.

Technology use related objectives:

As noted in the results, there was no reference to the technology use related objectives, which appear to be more of a list of objects students will engage with, rather than objectives. It is apparent from the video that the robots that were constructed used these components.

Teamwork skills:

Teamwork was one of the clearest themes emerging from the open coding of the interview, with further data emerging from the questionnaire and observations. Students engaged in team work and highlighted different aspects of working in a team that had been important, with some referring to teamwork in the mid-point reflection as their greatest achievement. However, while there is evidence to suggest that students are developing teamwork skills, due to lack of specificity in this objective, no clear conclusions can be drawn.

Creative thinking:

Similar to ‘develop creative thinking skills...’ above, there is evidence of creative thinking in idea generation but from the data no clear conclusions can be reached.

Presenting results:

There was no evidence from the data that students presented any results.

Problem solving:

There is very limited evidence of students engaging in problem solving, although they clearly did as they responded positively to questions about the problems they had been presented with. However the data provides no insight into the problem solving process or whether students learned anything about problem solving. As it is unclear from the observations and activity plan how much of the programme they wrote themselves (whether they were given a half-baked solution or a blank canvas), it is not possible to comment on the types of problem solving that they needed to do – for example it is unclear whether students had to first deconstruct code in order to understand it, before reconstructing it to solve a new problem.

Formulate and express ideas:

Through the discussion and interview, it is clear that students are able to formulate and express their ideas.

Listening skills:

Listening skills are important for teamwork and several students in both questionnaire and interview data mention the importance of listening. This appears to be one area that some students have developed a greater awareness of.

Decision making within a team:

It is clear that decisions were made within the teams but it is unclear how these decisions were made and what students learned.

Unexpected outcomes – maths:

Mathematics was not referred to in the activity plan as an objective but may have been a suitable domain from which objectives could have been identified as it is referred to in the sequence of activities and was broadly referred to in the interview and questionnaire.

In the reporting of the questionnaire data it was noted that there was a difference between children's perceptions of maths and science in their reported self-efficacy in terms of ease or difficulty of the subject in the pre-questionnaire. While most find maths easy, the results are less clear for science. Yet in the post-questionnaire 16 students reported that having completed the workshop they thought they were good at maths, 21 reported that they were good at science. This raises important questions about whether and how students' views of their own ability in relation to STEM subjects could both be positively or negatively affected by engaging in robotics activities. This will be an important area of analysis when exploring the data across all partners and raises important questions about how and why this might occur which can only be explored in interviews.

STEREOTYPES

Gendered roles and expectations were evident from the tutors' reflections, video observations and the reported experiences of Group 1. Particularly apparent was an initial assumption by the boys about the ability of the girls to make a valid contribution. While this appeared to be resolved on day one with tutor intervention, on day two there is evidence of it occurring again, with the girls either being excluded or excluding themselves from the activity. This continued until the boys surprised at what the girls had achieved in their absence. It is unclear whether this was fully resolved but the group did go on to work productively together. It would appear therefore that the ability of the girls to demonstrate what they could do had the potential to challenge the boys' assumptions, whether this is more effective than the tutor's intervention is impossible to say. However it is an authentic experience which has greater potential for changing people's understandings, in terms of their 'world view'.

Popular media appears to influence children's assumptions about scientists and while no firm conclusions can be drawn at this time, the evidence suggests that the workshop may have had some positive influence on these views. Equally it appears that there may have been some positive impact on attitudes towards STEM careers, if only temporarily. While three students had changed their

original answer about the job they would like to do to a STEM career after the workshop, this is insufficient evidence to suggest that there has been any meaningful or long lasting change for these students. However, it is clear from the interview that while students don't necessarily want scientists when they grow up, they can see the benefits of having robotic tools that they would work with in their future jobs and through this workshop they have some understanding of what robots are and how they work. The knowledge and understanding created in this workshop at this young age provides a memorable and credible knowledge base upon which they can build and test new information they encounter. Whether this will have any impact on their choices of STEM careers or their experiences as adults using and interacting with robots in their daily lives is yet to be determined.

4.2 MALTA

Results:

CONTEXT AND ACTIVITY PLAN:

This case study explores the 'Introduction to Dash and Dot' workshop in Malta, in which the primary domain is technology and there are curriculum links to mathematics and ICT. The activity plan was designed by a commercial company with experience in teacher professional development, for children aged 8-10 with no prior knowledge of robotics or programming, it was run on this occasion with children between the ages of 8 and 9. The subject related objectives were:

- Introducing basic programming
- Applying basic programming to mathematical concepts

Further objectives identified in the activity plan relate to the Dash and Dot robot and the applications that go with it, discussions to find solutions, teamwork, groups assisting each other and exploration to find solutions. It is clear that not all of these are objectives as defined by educationalists, as they do not define what students should be able to do by the end of the workshop. Introducing basic programming, for example, could only be an objective for the teacher. However, applying basic programming to mathematical concepts is a measurable objective for students. Although the activity plan mentions links to the mathematics and ICT curriculum it is unclear what these are.

This highlights an area for development through the Framework and Activity plan, to provide guidance on the construction of objectives. As the activity plan in this case is presented using the revised activity plan (presented in D4.1), this suggests that further dialogue between partners about the design and use of these activity plans will be valuable in their development.

While it is stated in the activity plan that no prior knowledge is required, it appears from the activity plan that children would need to have some existing knowledge of at least some of the mathematical concepts, e.g. the properties of an equilateral triangle. There is no evidence to suggest that these are taught in the activity plan.

Only one child mentioned that they had any previous experience of programming, which was in Minecraft, so it is unclear what they child did or if they have an accurate understanding of programming.

The activity is planned for two half days, totalling 8 hours, although the total sequence of activities is longer than this. On the first day 22 students participated and on the second 24. The change in participation is not unexpected. Participation in workshops which are implemented over more than one day within a standard school day are likely to be affected by typical school absence.

Each team was comprised of two children, who were paired based on alphabetical order (the school's choice), meaning that there is no bias in the allocation or selection of students within teams. In total there were 12 teams which took part in the activity in the school hall. Each group was provided with a large sheet of paper or mat and were told that they had to stay within their space to avoid them running around. In total there were 4 mixed gender teams, 6 all-male teams and 2 all-female teams, one of which only participated on the second day.

During the workshop, children were expected to exchange ideas, discuss, collaborate, compete and maintain a constant collaborative role. Students were instructed to share the robot and tablet, with which they programmed and controlled the robot, equally. The student activities included writing, observing, constructing, discussing, negotiating, exploring and solving. The learning processes emphasised relate to: analysis of robot behaviours, suggesting a black-box or grey-box approach; and direct instruction. However, as with the objectives mentioned above, it is unclear what the learning process is, except for analysis. Additionally, in the first phase of the sequence of activities emphasis is given to exploration which is not mentioned in this section of the activity plan. Again, this appears to be an aspect that the Framework and Activity Plan could be developed to further support.

During the workshop tutors were expected to support, intervene, facilitate and teaching, through demonstrations, setting challenges and intervening is students got stuck. Teaching and learning approaches which were not mentioned under this heading but are revealed in the sequence of activities include direct instruction through presentations and what is presumed to be teacher-mediated or teacher-led discussion.

In the revised Activity Plan, a section on student productions presents the artefacts, programmes and discussions that students are expected to create and engage with. These provide a tangible outcome to the workshop which could be measured and assessed, although not mentioned in this workshop activity plan. These could and possibly should also be related to the objectives stated at the start of the document.

In this activity plan, the student productions provide a clear sense of what the students will be creating and would be invaluable to another teacher attempting to use this activity plan. The only section that is less clear is the section on discussions which are somewhat vague. For example it is unclear if the "description of a situation" is achieved by students or the tutors. Based on the sequence and description of activities, it appears that this is a tutor task and from this students go away to solve the problem and presumably discuss potential solutions in the process.

Similarly the sequence of activities is generally clear and could be implemented by another teacher. The first phase includes 2 teacher-centred presentations, a whole class discussion and orientation/familiarisation time with the technology through free exploration and set tasks. In the second phase (sequential programming) there are 6 highly structured tasks which are student centred. The third starts with a teach-centred presentation of a pseudo-real world scenario. It is unclear if there is any whole-class discussion of this or whether students are directed to discuss this in their pairs as they start to solve the problem. It is presumed that having created a possible solution to the problem, students are then instructed to "try to find a way to simplify their programmes". However it is unclear as to how this phase should be operationalised, or how the students would

learn how to simplify their programmes. One interesting aspect of this phase is the clear role of the teacher as a more knowledgeable other in the second half of the activity. The fourth phase continues to focus on group work with students presented with puzzles to complete. However it is unclear what the tutor and students are doing in this phase, or how they should learn to test the programme, etc. The fifth phase is much clearer, relating to instruction in previous section and presenting clear tasks. One point for consideration is how the first of the two tasks listed, which is described as particularly challenging, could be scaffolded to move the activity into the zone of proximal development for each child. The final phase involves feedback and evaluation which includes the creation of a postcard to a friend to let them know about their experience over the two workshop days. This is particularly interesting in relation to Papert's (n.d.) suggestion that "the building of robotic devices acquires "writability" because it lends itself to stage-by-stage description". These were used to capture students' reflections of the two days and are discussed below.

Overall the sequence of activities contain a balanced mix of teacher as instructor and guide-on-the-side. This is seen in the tutor reflection sheets from the first day which suggest that the majority of their time was spent supporting groups rather than providing whole class instruction. However, what is not clear is how tutor support is given, whether there is a tendency to show children what they need to know or to guide them to finding the solution for themselves. The latter can be more challenging and time consuming.

The assessment procedures are currently incomplete beyond the original template suggestions. However it may be possible for the tutors to use the interview with the focus group to explicitly assess engagement with and success in the objectives.

OBSERVATIONS

Within the field notes three groups are mentioned. Group 2 were observed helping Group 1 (both all-male teams). There is no further detail and the time was not noted but this does allow us to infer that the social and action related objective 'groups assisting each other to work out activities' did occur. However it should also be noted that in conversation with one of the tutors as part of member checking in the data analysis process, she mentioned that in practice they tried to avoid this as it was felt that "children running around in the classroom would increase panic and noise" and they wanted to make sure that the data collected actually belonged to the team it was collected from. Therefore this observation is useful in assessing the artefacts of learning below. The other group mentioned was composed of 2 female students who were noted to be "moving on rapidly and progressing faster than the rest of the class".

From the analysis of the video data, it is clear that there were some groups that did not work as effectively as others. For example, within the focus group one boy maintains control of the tablet whilst the two sit together. The same child is the one seeks assistance/clarification. Figure 1 shows the same child standing at the race track as he runs the programme and observes the robot, moving the robot when it crashes. During which, his partner (white socks to the right of the picture) remains seated.

Figure 1 Focus group testing their programme on the race track.

It is unclear whether the seated child has disengaged from the activity or is simply letting the other boy have his turn and it is with respect to this that other comments made by the students in relation to sharing and taking turns is queried. Shortly after this episode the standing child can be seen relaying information to the child on the floor and the seated child is seen pointing, suggesting that this is some communication as part of problem solving. However shortly after this, the seated child can be seen throwing pieces of paper at the race track which would be classified as a disruptive behaviour.

Of further note is the group next to the focus group (group 4). This is a mixed gender group, in which the boy starts by holding the tablet and the girl is seen pointing and manipulating things on the screen, before taking it away from him (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Tablet taken from the boy by the girl

Shortly after this, the girls calls to her teacher. The teacher bends forwards to look at the tablet, whilst the girl leans forward with it in her hands. The boy is seen at some points to lean forward or look at the teacher before quickly starting to disengage, looking around the room and leaning back against the wall, before the female teacher bends down and female student leans in, both looking at

the tablet (Figure 3). While the reasons for the original taking of the tablet and the female teacher and student appearing to block the boy, or the boy physically withdrawing from the interaction cannot be assumed; the results of this interaction are clear. As the teacher continues to interact with the female student, the boy watches from his position against the wall, before getting up and walking away without speaking. Neither teacher, nor the girl react when he does this.

Figure 3 Boy leans back against the wall as teacher and student move closer

When the boy returns, neither the teacher nor student acknowledge him. He stands, leaning against the wall, looking at their interaction at first before looking around the room, as the girl picks up the robot and appears to explain something to the teacher. Within this interaction exclusionary and potentially gendered behaviour is observed, however, while the literature would draw us to the assumption that boys will exclude girls due to gender stereotypes, this does not appear to be happening in this instance. Over the next 15 minutes the boy is seen re-engaging but for limited periods of time, whilst the girl remains in control of the tablet throughout.

Another interpretation of this episode and the earlier one is that the children are turn-taking, with one solving the first puzzle, the other the next. If this is the case, then it is clear that there is no opportunity to develop essential collaboration and communication skills which educational robotics activities provide rich opportunities for. However moments before these two episodes, one of the tutors calls for the attention of the whole class and points out that she has seen only one person using the tablet and as a result they are “not discussing and going round in circles”, yet we see two groups in which one person controls the tablet and does the work, whilst the other disengages.

Over this same period of the workshop, there are two particularly notable actions of the tutors. The first is the direct instruction of students to work as a team but without scaffolds or supports from the tutor. The other is when tutors are helping children to understand why their programme is not working, or to understand the task. Here the tutors can be observed to act as a guide. While there is evidence of tutors guiding the thinking of the students through concrete, observable actions, there is a tendency to rely on more abstract explanations. For example, one tutor is heard ‘talking through’

the code of one group and explaining what would happen. From a constructionist and experiential learning perspective, observable actions are more powerful for learning, particularly at this age where children are considered to have limited ability for abstract thought.

STUDENT REFLECTIONS

Due to the young age of the students, it was agreed between the lead researcher and the tutors that the children could do a “write a postcard to a friend” activity, in place of a reflective blog. This was given to the students to write about the first and second day and completed in groups. Each task had some written prompts but except for group 9 these were mostly ignored.

Most teams provided a short account of the day, which typically included the words “fun” and “best day ever”. Within these descriptions some teams identified that they had learned what robots do and how to programme them. Both puzzles and competition are mentioned, as was a robotics experiment by one team. This suggests that different activities appealed to different teams. One team made reference to sharing the tablet and another to taking-turns. At the end of day 1, group 6 were anticipating that “we’re going to complete it next time”, and reported on day 2 a sense of achievement having completed the puzzles.

TUTOR REFLECTIONS

Following each of the workshops, tutors were asked to complete a reflection on the day. Only two tutors completed a reflection for the first session. However these reflections provide a number of valuable personal observations from that day and helps to reveal some of their actions, and what they have learnt from the workshop themselves.

Both tutors referred to the fact that programming robots was new for the children and suggested that resulted in positive engagement. However they also noted that “some were prepared about robots” as evidenced in the introduction to the workshop, which may have been due to their awareness of robots through popular media or because their parents or teachers had talked to them ahead of the day.

Each tutor identified an interesting barrier to engagement. The first was reading, which was a barrier to understanding the instructions for a couple of children. However it was noted by the tutor that once the instructions had been read to the students they understood what to do. Reading is a key skill, and limited knowledge is a potential barrier when tasks are given in written form only. It is also required to write programmes when using a block-based language, however there was no mention of the students struggling to create their programmes due to reading difficulties. Additionally, in this case all instructions were provided in English, as is the programming environment. However, while some children stated that they spoke both English and Maltese at home, some only identified Maltese which may indicate less familiarity with English.

The second barrier was the user interface, about which the tutor commented that “finding the menus tabs on the tablet was not straight forward” and “those children who were not exposed to drag and drop concepts grasped them soon after we showed them and explained”. While both user interface issues were easily remedied, meaning that there was a low-barrier or threshold to engagement, they highlight issues of user interface design for this age group and both designers’ and teachers’ assumptions of the knowledge and experience young children have with technology.

One of the tutors noted that “the students were all receptive to learning and trying out the activities; they asked when they got stuck but got on”. This suggests that the students had a positive sense of self-efficacy around the tasks that they were given, engaging in their own explorations of possible solutions and only asking for help when they hit a seemingly intractable problem.

At the end of the first session, one of the tutors noted that they had introduced a free exploration of the robot when it was first given to the children, before they began any tasks. This is mentioned in the activity plan. They felt that this had been a positive action and so it was implemented in all subsequent workshops.

INTERVIEWS

Following the final workshop, group 6 was invited to participate in a short interview (8 minutes) about their experiences during the workshop. Both open and structured analysis of the interview was undertaken and the results are presented here.

There were two boys in the group that was interviewed and it was clear that within the group they self-organised within their group:

“I: *Ok issa fill grupp tagħkom min għamel xiex? X'amiltu?*

Ok, now tell me in your group, who did what and what did you do?

C2: *Erm , aħna dejjem nixxerjaw darba jien u darba perezempju n, naqta jien u darba I take you*

Erm, we always share, once myself and once the other for example

I: *Orrajt igifieri kif iddicidejtu ħadtuha in turns jew kulhad jagħmel li jrrid ?*

Ok, how did you decide, did you take it in turns or else everyone does whatever they wish?

C2: *Hadniha in turns*

We took it in turn “

Although it is unclear exactly how the turn-taking took place, it would appear from later comments that the students worked together, rather than one person doing one puzzle and the other the next. One person may have been in control but in so, they worked together and by working together they were able to learn.

The children said that the workshop was interesting and one of the children who had previously attended a robotics fair said that although he hadn't learned anything new, this workshop was more fun. The other child stated that he had found that learning about what robots can do was particularly interesting. They both identified puzzle 5 on the first day of the workshop as the most challenging task but it is unclear as to why.

When asked what they had learned, they mentioned the importance of teamwork and demonstrated a sense of self-efficacy around programming robots.

They had a positive perception of science. Although the pronoun ‘he’ was used to describe scientists, when asked, the students said that both girls and boys could be scientists. They were characterised as being precise and persistent with their experiments, although their description began to move towards popular culture stereotypes:

- “C1: Sci, scientists never need to give up because they they need to experiment always, er and even they have to they have to what’s the word, experiment
- I: Mhm
- C1: B, because if they don’t experiment things will go very wrong and even killing human beings”

ARTEFACTS OF LEARNING

As part of the first day activities, students were required to write down their solution to each puzzle. They provide a rich data source showing what students completed during the activities and their level of engagement. By comparing solutions by groups across time and solutions to the same problem from different groups, we can see that some students become aware of different aspects of the code and choose to ignore others. For example, in the artefacts created for the first puzzle, we notice that although the groups all created the same programme, they report it differently (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Examples of written programmes from 3 teams for Puzzle 1

While group 1 (robot number 1) (all-male group) provides text only, both groups 2 (all-male) and 3 (mixed) provide a more graphical representation which resembles to different extents the programming environment itself.

ROBOT NUMBER: <u>Al-Dash-1</u>	STUDENT CODES: ROBOT NUMBER: <u>2</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: <u>Puzzle 2</u>	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>3</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: <u>Puzzle 2</u>
WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• when start✓• Look right 90✓• Look Left 90.		Look <u>right</u> 90 Look <u>Left</u> 90
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• When start• Look <u>right</u> 90• Look <u>Left</u> 90	

Figure 5 Programmes for puzzle 2

In Figure 5, group 2 have decided that a graphically less accurate representation is acceptable, however they and group 3 have kept the shapes around the numbers, as per the user interface. However at this point group 3 stops writing “when start”, an important part of the programme, without which it would not run. This continues in puzzle 3 (Figure 6) at which point group 2 has started reporting their code in a text only style, with bullet points marking each line of code. In puzzle 3, students are told to “Make Dash turn all lights red and then turn them to green”. As can be seen in Figure 6, if the code presented by group 3 is representative of the code they had created, they did not complete this task.

ROBOT NUMBER: <u>1</u>	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>2</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: <u>Puzzle 3</u>	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>3</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: <u>Puzzle 3</u>
WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• when start✓• All lights red✓• All lights green.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• When start• All Lights Red• All lights Green	Lights red All Lights

Figure 6 Programmes for puzzle 3

ROBOT NUMBER: <u>1</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: _____	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>2</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: _____	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>3</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: <u>Puzzle 4</u>
WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When Start v • Forward 50 fast v • All lights red v • All lights green v • Look Left 90 v • turn left 90 v • Forward 50 fast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When Start v • Forward 50 fast v • All lights green v • All lights red v • Look left 90 v • Turn Turn left 90 v • Look forward 90 	<p>dash looked left</p> <p>dash</p> <p>Forward</p> <p>Lock forward</p> <p>All Lights</p>

Figure 7 Programmes for puzzle 4

Whilst groups 1 and 2 continue to fully report the code that they have used in written form. Group 3 is still under reporting, using only key words and sometimes providing a description rather than words used in the programming interface (see Figure 7), suggesting there is an emerging issue within this group. This continues on to puzzle 7 (Figure 8), at which point if statements have been introduced. However there is no evidence to suggest that group 3 is aware of this statement type.

ROBOT NUMBER: <u>1</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: _____	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>2</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: _____	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>3</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: <u>Puzzle 7</u>
WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when start v • Repeat forever • If Dash object Behind • say wheel • Turn Right 180 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when start v • If Dash obstacle in front • say wheel • Backward 50 fast 	<p>We made dash say 'uh' and turn round</p>

Figure 8 Programmes for puzzle 7

ROBOT NUMBER: <u>1</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: _____	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>2</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: _____	ROBOT NUMBER: <u>3</u> NAME OF ACTIVITY: <u>Puzzle 8</u>
WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK	WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when start v • Repeat forever • If Dash object Behind • say wheel • Turn Right 180 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when start v • If Dash obstacle in front • say wheel • Backward 50 fast 	<p>We made dash say 'uh' and turn round</p>

Figure 9 Programmes for puzzle 8

Reporting puzzle 8, neither groups 2 or 3 demonstrate awareness of the 'forever' loop. Additionally it is worth noting in Figure 9 that group 1 has begun to use notation similar to the graphical programming language to show how the programme is nested. This may be because the reporting of

the programme has become more complex and is less clear in written form. Group 2 does a similar thing in puzzle 9 when they first use nesting Figure 10.

STUDENT CODES: _____

ROBOT NUMBER: 2 NAME OF ACTIVITY: Puzzle 9

WRITE DOWN THE PROGRAM YOU HAVE WRITTEN TO MAKE YOUR ROBOT WORK

When Start

- o Repeat Forever
- o If Dash hears Voice
 - o Turn Right
 - o Turn left
- o If Dash picked up
 - o say sigh

Figure 10 Group 2's programme for puzzle 9

What these artefacts of learning demonstrate is evidence of which groups have engaged with which programming concepts. While group 3 may have simply used a short-form of the code to report what they did, even if they used if statements, forever loops and nesting in their original code, there is no evidence to suggest that they understood how these worked.

The changes that occurred in the reporting of the programmes is also interesting if considered in relation to the observation and tutor's comment, discussed above, which highlights that while these two groups did cooperate at some point, this was generally discouraged in case it should mean that students report what other groups did, rather than themselves. What this does not take account of is that this type of inter-group sharing of ideas can help children to identify what is and is not important in what they report. Although no conclusions can be drawn from these speculations, they indicate an area for further investigation throughout the workshops.

As part of the second day, images were captured of the robots that were created which show some creative modifications to the robots to get them to draw as they move.

QUESTIONNAIRE

The pre- and post-workshop provide useful background information about students and provide a snapshot of their perceptions of the workshop. In this case, 23 students completed both the pre-workshop and post-workshop questionnaire. It should be noted that not all responses reported in the tables below add up to the number of respondents for each questionnaire as some children did not answer some questions. It was noted by the tutors that one child required the questions to be read to them and that another appeared to have dyslexia. However the overall response for each item was high.

Between the pre- and post-workshop questionnaires children’s job aspirations remained constant, although two children misunderstood the first question. In total 8 students in the pre-questionnaire and 9 in the post-questionnaire expressed an interest in STEM careers.

Beyond paper drawings, none of the students reported that they had ever created a robot. As mentioned in the interview data, one child had attended a robotics fair where they said that they had done some programming in Minecraft, however without previous experience this is questionable.

The pre-questionnaire was designed to provide baseline data on each student, to characterise the individual case; for comparison across cases and between countries; and to identify students whose data would be particularly interesting to analyse in depth.

Of the 23 students that completed the pre-workshop questionnaire, 14 identified STEM subjects as their favourite. Reasons included their general enjoyment of the subject, mentioning aspects such as solving problems, learning about plants, fun and interest. For some the reasons given were related to their positive sense of self-efficacy, such as “because I am good at it”. 9 students identified STEM subjects as the ones that they liked the least, with the difficulty of these subjects and a negative sense of self-efficacy the main reasons.

All but one child who identified a STEM subject as their least favourite chose maths. To understand students’ perceptions of maths and science, a series of statements were responded to on a Likert-scale (reported in Table 5 and Table 6 respectively), followed by a question as to whether the students would like to study maths and science when they are older.

Table 11 Pre-questionnaire Likert responses to statements about maths.

Statement	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
In general I find maths easy	13	1	8
Maths lessons are boring	7	1	13
We have fun in maths lessons	12	3	5
Maths is important for the job I want to do	13	4	4
My teacher thinks I am good at maths	16	3	2
I get good grades in maths	17	1	1
I have to work on my own in maths	12	1	7
Maths is the most interesting subject in school	12	4	4
Maths is important to learn	19	1	0
Most of the students in my class are good at maths	15	3	2

Exploring their responses to the math efficacy questions (Table 5), it can be seen that a clear majority of students think that they get good grades and their teacher thinks that they are good at maths. Additionally students recognise the importance of learning maths. However their experience of

maths lessons is less positive. There may be no correlation but in the post-questionnaires the children were largely unaware of using their knowledge of maths in the workshop, although the workshop has been designed for the domain of mathematics.

Reviewing the Likert-scale responses to statements on science (Table 6), we see that these students have both a high sense of self-efficacy and enjoyment of the subject.

Table 12 Pre-questionnaire Likert responses to statements about science.

Statement	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
Science is the most interesting subject in school	16	2	2
In general I find science easy	17	2	1
Science lessons are boring	1	0	19
We have fun in science lessons	19	1	0
Science is important for the job I want to do	11	5	4
My teacher thinks I am good at science	17	1	0
I have to work on my own in science	16	1	3
I think science is difficult	18	1	1
I get good grades in science	17	0	1
Most of the student in my friends are good at science	17	2	1

Of particular interest are three students who identified STEM subjects as both their most and least enjoyed subjects. Two students whose favourite subjects were science disliked maths, and the opposite was true for the third student, all referring to the difficulty of their least favourite subject.

While some students had stated they liked maths “because I like solving problems”, others identified maths as their least favourite subject because “it has problems”. This raises questions about the types of problems that children are given in both school and educational robotics workshops, but are beyond the scope of this project. However we see in Table 4 that there are split views about problem solving for this group of students who have an uncertain sense of self-efficacy as a whole.

Table 13 Pre-questionnaire Likert responses to statements about themselves.

Statement	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
I like using computers	20	1	1
I know a lot about robots	11	2	10
I learn best with other people	16	4	3
I like science	19	4	4
I like maths	12	4	7
I like working on my own	13	2	8
I like working in teams	22	1	0
I like trying to solve difficult problems	15	0	8
I need help solving problems	15	4	4
I am good at solving problems	15	2	6
I want to understand more about mechanical things	16	0	7
I want to solve problems that can help people	22	1	0
I prefer tasks that only have one correct answer	13	2	7

I like to keep working on a project until it is perfect	22	1	0
I like it when I can solve problems quickly	21	1	1
I think it is important to learn about science	18	4	0
I like learning about how things work	22	0	0

Although problem solving is an issue for some children before the workshop, by the end 20 of the 22 children who responded agreed that they would like to try solve more challenges like the ones they were presented with in the workshop.

After the workshop a second questionnaire was distributed, which aimed to assess the impact of the workshop. Table 7 shows the responses of the children to the problems which they had to solve during the workshop. Here we see that while most found the problems fun and interesting, some still found them difficult. The two students (boy and girl) who reported that they did not find the problems interesting, did agree that they were difficult, so we can reasonably assume that the problems were not interesting to these students because they were too easy. These students were in the same group, group 4, and their written code shares characteristics of the group 3 artefacts of learning. So it could be suggested that disinterest may have resulted in limited engagement, however they both strongly agreed that the problems were fun and at a later point in the questionnaire both strongly agreed that what they were doing was interesting. Regardless, there was an issue which is likely to have influenced the decision of the girl to give the workshop 2 out of 5 stars, when all others gave it either 4 or 5. This highlights the importance of having several data point for the same question but this also increases the length of questionnaires, a point which is returned to in the evaluation of the evaluation kit in year 1 in D6.2.

Table 14 Post-questionnaire Likert responses to the workshop problems

The problems we had to solve were...	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
Interesting	20	0	2
Difficult	14	3	4
Fun	21	1	0

While most students had stated that they liked working in teams and learned best with other people, the students had mixed views about the difficulty of working in teams (Table 8). This is an interesting response when compared to students' responses to statements about what they did during the workshop (Table 9).

Table 15 Post-questionnaire perceptions of working in a team

Working in a team was...	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
Interesting	17	3	1
Difficult	9	3	9
Fun	19	1	1

In Table 9 there it is clear that some students felt that they gave up too quickly, but more importantly in this case it is clear that there are issues around teamwork with many students agreeing or strongly

agreeing that they worked on their own and felt that people did not listen to them. Equally with several students disagreeing or strongly disagreeing with the statements related to being encouraged by their team and helping to programme the robot. This raises important questions about these children's concepts of teamwork (with most stating that they worked as part of a team) and how teamwork can be facilitated in these settings. The latter is an important point for consideration in the development of the Framework and Activity Plan.

Table 16 Post-questionnaire Likert responses to statements about the workshop

During the workshop ...	(Strongly) Agree	Neither	(Strongly) Disagree
I identified a problem to solve	16	4	3
I worked on something that I was interested in	22	1	0
I tried to solve an important problem	19	1	3
I worked as part of a team	21	1	1
I worked on my own	7	1	15
I helped programme a robot	16	2	5
I was able to choose what I wanted to do	11	6	5
I feel that other people did not listen to me	10	2	10
I did most of the work	15	3	4
I was encouraged by my team	13	3	6
I worked hard	19	1	2
I was bored	2	2	18
I liked sharing what I had done with other people	15	3	4
I helped someone	17	3	2
I gave up too quickly	9	3	10

In these responses we can see that only 1 student disagreed with the statement that they had worked as part of a team and 1 neither agreed not disagreed. One of these students had agreed that working in a team was difficult and the other had chosen not to answer this question. Interestingly, these two students (1 girl, 1 boy) had worked in the same team. From the artefacts of learning there is little evidence of them not engaging, all but one of the puzzles has been completed, although 2 are incomplete. However examining further questionnaire responses from these students it can be seen that they viewed themselves as working on their own, not encouraged by their team mate and not listened to. Thus this team appears to have been dysfunctional in some way and this raises an important issue for the Framework and Activity Plan: How to plan for and support teams that do not function as anticipated.

Technology and science stand out as the two subjects which students identified as the ones that they applied knowledge from and gained knowledge about from working with robots. Whilst technology is unsurprising, science in this context would be. However it links to the students' (as a whole) positive views of science and the idea of experimenting (mentioned in the children's reflections) as something that is done in science.

The linked curriculum domain identified in the activity plan was maths and the associated objective was to apply basic programming to mathematical concepts. As there was no intention for maths to be learned, it is unsurprising that only 2 students reported that the robots helped them to learn more about maths. It may have been surprising to see that only 4 students identified that they had used their knowledge of mathematics whilst working with the robots, however, on reviewing the tasks that

students had to complete there was very little mathematical knowledge or thinking that was required.

When asked what they had learned about themselves from the workshop, some students mentioned that they had realised they were good at solving problems, an issue raised above as it was commonly associated with a dislike of maths. Others mentioned more personal attributes: “that I don’t give up quickly” and “I need to pay more attention in class”. However most mentioned a sense of self-efficacy around programming which had been new for almost all students.

Asked about what they had learned about working with robots, the children have range of answers from conceptual and technical to enjoyment.

With the previously raised issues about teamwork, the answers to the question ‘What have you learned about working with other people’ were particularly interesting to compare to their experiences and issues with teamwork. In addition to learning skills such as sharing, the children demonstrated an appreciation for teamwork with some stating that it was fun and enjoyable.

Overall the workshop was awarded on average 4.6 stars out of 5, suggesting that while there are clear areas for development through the Framework, overall the children enjoyed their experience.

Discussion

In this section, three emerging themes from the data are discussed in further detail. These have been selected as they were common across data sets and therefore present a stronger base from which to draw some initial conclusions, based only on this case study.

EVIDENCE OF LEARNING

This section explores each of the learning objectives identified in the activity and presents evidence on whether students engaged with this objective and whether they achieved it. In some cases this is complicated due to skills or objects listed rather than clear objectives and so in these instances relevant data is discussed from the perspectives of learner engagement and knowledge acquisition.

Applying basic programming concepts to mathematical concepts

While there is clear evidence that the children gain an understanding of basic programming concepts, there is limited evidence to suggest that these were applied to mathematical concepts. To address this, the objectives in the activity plan and sequence of events may need to be more explicit, providing at least one example within the sequence of activities which is explicitly aligned to the objective. Additionally the objectives may need to be broken down to make it clear to another teacher who is considering using the activity plan, exactly which programming concepts will be used and how they align to which mathematical concepts, on the assumption that the activity plans need to be accessible to the many teachers who have little or no experience of programming. This needs to be considered as part of the development of the Framework and Activity Plan.

This assertion is supported by evidence from the post-questionnaire in which students only 2 students stated that they had learned anything about maths. However the links to maths were not explicit for the children, with only 4 stating that they had used maths to solve the problems.

Discussions between students to find the best solutions

There is insufficient evidence to confirm or refute that discussions took place between students to find the best solution. The video evidence of the focus group suggests that this does happen, but what the conversation is about in relation to the task is unclear.

Exploring to find solutions

In the activity plan it is clear from the sequence of activities that students were provided with opportunities to explore to find solutions, with evidence from other data sources showing that some children made an explicit connection to what they did in the workshop with experiments. However a question remains as to what extent the tutors supported or showed the students what to do when they became stuck and asked for help. With three tutors in the room, this averaged as one tutor per four groups, however the tutors were often seen standing waiting for the students to ask them questions, which suggests that the students were left to explore and solve the tasks by themselves.

Groups assisting each other to work out activities

In general there were few interactions between groups, so there is little evidence to suggest that groups assisted each other. For example, in the field notes Group 2 were observed helping Group 1 (both all-male teams) but there is no further detail and from the video data there is little further evidence. However this is perhaps unsurprising, as one of the tutors commented that in practice they tried to avoid this as it was felt that “children running around in the classroom would increase panic and noise” and they wanted to make sure that the data collected actually belonged to the team it was collected from. While this is helpful in the assessment of the artefacts of learning, it means that this learning objective needs to be reconsidered as the children are generally discouraged from this form of interaction.

Introducing basic programming concepts

There is evidence to show that the students were introduced to different programming concepts but the extent to which they were shown or discovered them for themselves through exploration is unclear.

Team work

It is clear from the data presented above that there were mixed experiences of team work across the groups and this is discussed in further detail below. From the perspective of learning about teamwork, it is clear from responses to the questionnaire that some students recognised they had learned or learned the importance of skills such as sharing. However it is unclear from the objective whether students were expected to ‘do’ team work or learn about it.

Use Dash and Dot

Throughout the workshop the children used Dash and Dot.

TEAM WORK

While the students report in the questionnaire that they engaged in teamwork, parts of the questionnaire data and video observations suggest that this was not always the case. There appear to be a number of factors that may need to be considered when this workshop is implemented in the future, including how the groups are formed, what instruction is given to the students about how they should share and when and how a tutor could identify and eventually intervene in a

dysfunctional team. The latter could be considered as part of the development of the Framework and Activity Plan but will require substantial engagement with this area of research.

MIXED GENDER GROUPS

In relation to team work, of particular interest during this workshop is the negative experience described by and observed of each of the 4 mixed gender groups.

In the post-workshop questionnaire, only 1 student disagreed with the statement that they had worked as part of a team and 1 neither agreed nor disagreed. These two students were in the same group (11) and had either agreed that working in a team was difficult or chosen not to answer this question in the questionnaire. The video data also demonstrates exclusionary behaviour which would contribute to the lack of team identity.

The artefacts of learning are another source of information on potentially dysfunctional teams. It was noted earlier that group 3 appeared to have disengaged with the workshop activity in the recording of their programmes and in the first reflective task they only wrote 5 words “wi did robots driving lights”, when all other groups filled or almost filled the space available. They also tended to give negative responses in the post-questionnaire.

Although single-gender groups also experienced difficulties with team work, mixed pairs appear to have experienced the greatest difficulties in this case. The reasons for this are not clear and may relate to typical school and home experiences of the children. This is beyond the scope of this research. However this does not mean that single-gender groups is the solution, particularly as STEM careers are dominated by men and there are many reports gendered assumptions and treatment of women in such work places which dissuades women from pursuing careers in these fields. Thus it is important that both implicit and explicit assumptions and behaviours around gender need to be considered and challenged.

5 FINDINGS OF SINGLE COUNTRY ANALYSIS

This section presents the findings of the Greek country analysis. The evaluation was based on the following evaluation criteria which are used to structure this section of the report.

1. Learner engagement
2. Changing & sustaining attitudes to STEM
3. Connecting STEM to society
4. Creativity
5. Collaborative working
6. Entrepreneurial activity
7. Questions for using specific tools
8. What works, for whom and in what circumstances?
9. Plans for further development of activities.

As the aim of this analysis is to evaluate the pre-kit and whether it is fit for purpose in evaluating the ER4STEM Framework in years 2 and 3, the results reported aim to provide sample episodes to demonstrate how each source of data contributes. The implications of these findings are discussed in section 7.

5.1 LEARNER ENGAGEMENT

Students were engaged in different STEM concepts through the workshops. The engagement with concepts related to Technology and Engineering was present all the time due to the nature of the activities which demanded mostly programming and construction of the robot. Apart from this, there were also engagement with mathematical and physics concepts, in a less extent though.

The following episode is an example from UoA 414 workshop where students are engaging with the concept of repetition structure in programming. They are trying to make their robot move on a square and they are arguing about the number and the order of commands, concluding that they will need to use a loop block to repeat them.

41412: Here I will write the commands 4 times.

41403: No you need them 2 times

41412 : Why not 4?

41403 : Because these are 2 commands for the 2 sides of the square, thus we need these 2 commands one more time in order to have the 4 sides.

41403: Actually we need a block that will repeat what we write...

41409: I found it! It is the loop!

The engagement with different scientific fields of STEM is also evident from the answers of the students to the post questionnaires and interviews. One important result that came of the data analysis is that many students realized the combination of multiple STEM fields in robotics and the connection between them (mathematics, physics, technology, etc.). Below are some of the students' answers that indicate their engagement with STEM concepts and the combination of STEM fields to robotics.

From UoA 417 interview

41704: I realized that it helps a lot in robotics if you know physics, especially for the feet and the movements. Also you need mathematics to build the skeleton of the robot. You need geometry to do the right measurements, to place on the right the materials etc.

T: So what knowledge from geometry do you think you need for the construction of a robot?

41717: First of all the degrees of the angles for the movements, also symmetry for the feet, and also you need geometry in order to make its body straight and stable.

Answers to the questionnaires

41718: I learned a lot of things about electrical circuits, about the design and the construction of a robot and a new programming language

41716 Robotics can be consider as a field of science which contains a lot of different fields such as computers, maths and physics

From UoA 415 interview

T: Did you use knowledge from other fields apart from programming?

41501: Yes. We used physics a lot. For example the robot didn't move, unless we put something rubbery on its feet to acquire friction. Moreover we had to consider gravity, because as the robot did big moves it fell down.

From UoA 416 post questionnaires

41612 (Q20): I learned to use technology in combination with my knowledge from other STEM fields

Below is another selected episode from workshop UoA 417, where a student explains to the teacher what his team has done in order to make the robot move. Through his explanations seems that he has used and understood significant concept related to electric circuits and engineering, such as grounding, voltage.

41717: I want to check the movement in order to decide where to put the legs of the robot

T: What did you do to make this move?

41706: First of all we wanted to ground another piece here so all this becomes 5 volts.

T: And what did you do to ground it?

41706: I used one cable and plug it to 5 volt of Arduino. Then I took another cable in order to connect the sensor and keep it on (the sensor). Then I used the cable that is for Arduino's data and plug it to port 9 as it was written in the code and a powered it.

From UoA 413 post questionnaires

41303 (Q20) In my opinion, working with robots is very interesting and useful for the future. In this workshop I learned how to program a robot. I also learned that if you give the right commands to the robot you will achieve your goal.

(Q 25) I had a great time and it was the first time that I used programming. This workshop helped me understand how important maths is, which I didn't find very important before

5.2 CHANGING & SUSTAINING ATTITUDES TO STEM

During all 7 workshops there were several incidents where students changed their attitude or their opinion about STEM. Through the analysis of the data, we located two basic categories of students' attitudes to STEM that changed through the workshops. The first category are students that considered STEM subjects as something difficult and hard to understand. These students believed that they weren't good at school subjects related to STEM and that they didn't have the abilities needed for robotics. After the robotics workshop they realized that STEM is not as hard as they thought and also that they are more capable. Thus, they gained self-confidence and changed their total view about STEM and their interest in future involvement in similar projects.

Below are 2 examples from the post questionnaires and the interview data that indicates this kind of change to the student's attitude towards STEM.

From UoA 414 post questionnaires:

41412 (Q18): I can succeed even in difficult tasks. In the past, I didn't used to engage with this field because I thought that it was difficult for me. But now I find it really interesting

From UoA 411 interview:

T: Has this workshop changed the way you see robots?

41128: I didn't believe that I could make a robot which will be able to move and do all this things, and now that I saw it and I understood how it works I liked it very much!

The other category includes students that had no interest in STEM and they considered STEM subjects as boring or something out of their personal interests. However, through the workshops they discovered an intriguing and interesting part of STEM and they became interested in those fields.

From UoA 413 interview

41335: To be honest, before the workshop I didn't like those subjects a lot but now I started to be more interested in them

T: So, has your opinion about STEM changed after this workshop?

41335: Yes. Because I never had thought to get involved with robotics and now that we worked on it I found it interesting

41339: And me too. When I was first told that I have to make a robot I thought that I will get bored and that I will not be able to do it. But then I saw that through collaboration we made it and that was great.

From UoA 413 post questionnaires

41306 (Q18): Although I don't like maths, I was able to use them and I understood you can achieve anything with hard work.

41335 (Q18): I learned my limits and not to be dogmatic about unknown things just because I have never done it before. Because when I firstly engaged with robotics I was negative about it but then I liked it very much and I wanted to continue

From UoA 416 post questionnaires

41622 (Q18): (She wants to become a nursery) I realized that I am interested in the robotics field

Moreover, most of the students argued that due to the practical nature of robotics, a similar workshop can influence other students to become interested in STEM.

From UoA 414 Interview

41403: I believe that a lot of students don't like some school subjects because they are taught only the theoretical parts. If they got involved in a more practical way they would like it more and they would have more interest for these subjects.

From UoA 415 Interview

T: Do you think that working with robots would help other students get interested in STEM?

41501: Yes of course, because in a way it is a practical application of the theoretical knowledge.

From UoA 413 Interview

T: Do you think that working with robots would help other students get interested in STEM?

41335: Yes because I also didn't like these subjects and this (means the robotics workshop) gives you a motivation to see from a different point of view these subjects and not take it for granted that you don't like them so you will not get involved with them.

41339: It is like a game. You put everything, mathematics, physics etc. altogether in a box.

Finally it is worth mentioning that some students changed their future job orientation towards a more STEM related choice. This result came from the students' answers to the question "When you finish school, what job would you like to do?" of pre and post questionnaires.

One selected example is a student from the workshop UoA413 who changed his answer from "Professional Boxer" to "Computer Technician" after the workshop. He also mentioned in the post questionnaire (Q25) that "My teacher taught me a lot of useful things which I will need because I want to become a Computer Technician".

Another example comes from a younger student who participated in workshop UoA412 and at the pre question answered that he/she hadn't decided yet, while at the post answered that he/she wants to work as an engineer. Moreover at the question "What have you learned about yourself?" (Q18) he/she noted "I discovered that I have a new skill"

5.3 CONNECTING STEM TO SOCIETY

The connection of STEM to society mostly took place either through conversations with the teacher or in the students' answers to the interviews.

One example comes from the workshop UoA 414 where the teacher had the students to do some brainstorming about robotics at the beginning of the activity. Through the brainstorming, students connected robots to real life activities and to the career field as well.

T: Why do we use the robots?

41410: They facilitate our lives

T: One example?

41408: In medicine

T: Of course! Have you heard about robotics in medicine? Sometimes scientists use robots to give instructions and perform an operation in a distant area that it does not have very good health equipment.

41405: Also to do works that are hard or dangerous for the human

41406: At home

41403: At factories, because robots are not getting tired like the human.

Moreover, this is evident from some students' answers to the interviews. For example the following two students from UoA 413 who argues that technology is very important in real life because a lot of everyday things are related to it.

T: Are you interested in technology, science, etc.?

41313: Yes because this helps us in real life. If you know how things work it can help you in other fields of your life

41322: Technology evolves as the years pass and many things are using technology, so if we know about it we will have the chance to use them.

In addition, the following answers of the post questionnaires indicate that students made a connection of STEM and robotics to society.

From UoA 413 post questionnaires

41360 (Q25): It was an interesting course in the field of informatics which helped us to understand how things from everyday life work and their strong connection to maths and physics

41323 (Q18): Through robotics I understood how everyday life things work and I realized that robotics can make us smarter

From UoA 417 post questionnaires

41704 (Q25): I liked it very much and I would love to have a similar job in the future

5.4 CREATIVITY

Creativity was spotted mostly during the constructing part, which also was the part that students referred to as the more "creative" or "challenging".

At workshop UoA 416 a student expressed an unexpected and unusual solution to a problem. Until this point the robot was programed to follow the wall to its right and now the students try to figure out what it will do if there is an empty space to its right. All the students express their ideas for the programming solution to the teacher, and all of the solutions include the use of an ultrasonic sensor to detect the distance and thus the empty space. However a student express the idea to use a colour sensor instead of the ultrasonic sensor, which is a creative solution.

41611: If we used the ultrasonic sensor to ensure that there is an open space in front.

41616: Maybe we could do it with the color sensor. For example if it detects its shadow

T: 41616 made a very good observation. He spoke about using color sensor in order to detect obstacles! This is a very nice and creative thought. You can use it because when the color sensor detects an obstacle returns a value and when there is nothing in front it returns the zero value.

Another characteristic example of students' creativity is evident on the following episode from workshop UoA 414. At the first session of the workshop the students' of focus group are trying to understand what the command "rotations" means and what its effect is on the robot. One student (41409) finds out that the command refers to the number of full rotations of the wheel and he tries to explain it to the other two students. In order to explain this he places a red Lego brick on the wheel and tell them to observe the brick's position as the wheel rotates. After their experimentation they conclude that "1 rotation" equals with 360 degrees or with a full rotation of the wheel.

41409 : Rotations is referred to one full rotation of the wheel. Look here. Write something on the duration

41403 writes '1 rotation' to the duration

41409 : Do you see this red brick? When the wheel would have rotated 360 degrees it will return here (the brick)

They test it on the floor and they follow the red brick with their finger

41409 ,41403 : Exactly 360 degrees!!

5.5 COLLABORATIVE WORKING

In all workshops, students worked in teams, usually consisted of 3-4 members. In the most cases they had a good collaboration in their team, though there were some incidents that they faced some collaboration problems as mentioned on the tutor's reflection. As came of the data analysis, students mostly worked in two ways in their team. Either they distributed roles and they formed smaller sub-teams to focus on different parts of the activity or they worked altogether on the same task.

In the video recordings data there are several incidents that show a collaboration between team members, usually expressed through argumentation about the solution to a problem or by through explanation of a concept from one student to another.

In the following episode from workshop UoA417, the student 41716 who is expert in programming explains to 41706 the functionality of multiple the commands in the program.

41706: But shouldn't it have a command telling the robot to stop making a sound?

41716: No look here the program. It says to the robot "if distance is 0 don't do anything". When the distance is this (points to the if command) do that.

41706: What are these? (He points to the command "tone")

41716: These are for the robot to beep.

41706: And here you say to the robot that if the distance is between 9 and 13, make a beep?

41716: Yes. Or else don't beep at all.

At the following episode a student from UoA 415 workshop explains to the teacher how they decided to work and what they did when they faced a problem. His description indicates a good collaboration between the team members.

T: When you faced a problem how did you solve it?

41503: First we all expressed our ideas and then we applied the idea that was more reasonable and that would make the robot work better.

T: And if this didn't work?

41503: We tried the other ideas

From the interviews and open questions of post questionnaires, it is clear that most students found the collaboration very useful to their work and mentioned it as an important factor to their successful completion of the activity.

From post questionnaires

41131 (Q19): It's better to collaborate than to work alone because through teamwork you can learn things which you didn't know

(Q18): Constructing a robot is difficult, so I worked hard and I learned through collaboration not to quit when things get more difficult

From UoA 411 interview of focus group

T: What have you learned about working in a team?

41102: In the team everything is completed easier and faster thanks to everyone's ideas

41101: We learn to listen to other's opinion and not only ours

41103: I learned how to work faster and I became more polite.

5.6 ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

In the activities that took place in this cycle of workshops, there was no entrepreneurial activity promoted, thus there is no relevant data,

5.7 WHAT WORKS, FOR WHOM AND IN WHAT CIRCUMSTANCES?

At this point in the data analysis process (year 1), it is not possible to infer what works, for whom and in what circumstances. However, as shown above and in the in-depth case studies earlier there is an emerging understanding of this which will be used to inform the development of the Framework.

5.8 PLANS FOR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF ACTIVITIES

After the workshops had finished, some students proposed ideas for further development of the workshops or for new robotics activities that they would like to get involved. These plans were expressed mostly in the interviews or in the post questionnaires.

From UoA 416 Interview

T: What would you change to make the activity even better?

41614: I would like to make the robot walk through a larger maze or through a harder maze with more obstacles and more exits.

From UoA 413 Interview

T: What would you change in the activity?

41323: I would like to give the robot the commands we want and not what the activity tells us.

From UoA 414 Interview

41409: I would like in the future to be in a robotics club.

After the UoA 417 workshop, students are discussing how they expected the workshop to be, what they liked and what not. At this conversation a girl from the specialty of engineers says that she would prefer to be a more engineer workshop and her classmate disagrees saying that if it was like this, students from other specialties couldn't participate.

41709: Before we begin the workshop, I believed that we will be given one real, human-like robot and that the teacher would have removed some cables, some resistors etc. and we would have to think how we will connect them in order to make it work. This would be better I think.

41702: Yes, we didn't expect to build everything from scratch. We thought that we would only connect some resistors, some capacitors etc.

41704: I actually preferred it that way.

41717: Yes it is better!

41709: Why? It would be better if it only needed electronics.

41717: But how would you collaborate with your team if it was only in your field?

41709: But ready-made robots have everything. For example it could be an electronic part we would fix, a programming part that the programmers would think etc.

41704: Yes but if it was so focused, the students that are electronics would manage it better and easier than the students from other fields. This is not nice.

This is a particularly interesting episode in relation to concepts of collaboration, the importance of team work and the added value of engaging with robotics for this purpose due to their interdisciplinary nature.

6 FINDINGS OF SINGLE DATA SETS

6.1 ACTIVITY PLANS

Pedagogic Evaluation

Across the 48 workshops, 13 different activity plans were implemented which covered a wide range of technologies, student ages settings and objectives. In Table 17 an overview of the activity plans created by the partners is presented. This includes the technologies they employ and the primary domain they cover, although all activity plans are multidisciplinary with their themes and tasks belonging to STE(A)M.

Table 17 Overview of the 13 workshops

No	Partner	Activity Plan	Technology	Domain - emphasis
1	AL - Malta	Introduction to Dash and Dot	Dash and Dot	Programming-mathematics
2	ESI-CEE	Introducing Robotics with Arduino, Scratch and Mindmaps	Custom set developed by ESI CEE	Programming – Engineering – creative thinking
3	TU-Wien	Learning basics of programming with Thymio II	Thymio II	Programming
4	TU-Wien	Crazy Robots	Mattie – custom set developed by TU-Wien	Engineering – Design - Business
5	PRIA	ECER-Botball Preparation Workshop	BotBall	Programming - Engineering
6	PRIA	European Conference on Educational Robotics	BotBall and any other robotic kit	Programming - Engineering
7	UoA-ETL	Making a robot “Smart” (introducing programming structures)	LEGO –NXT kit	Programming
8	UoA-ETL	Robotic “Safe Swing” and Seesaw	LEGO WEDO	Programming - Mathematics
9	UoA-ETL	Constructing and controlling a robot painter	LEGO –NXT - G	Programming - mathematics
10	UoA-ETL	Solving the maze problem with Lego EV3	Lego EV3	Programming
11	UoA-ETL	My first Robot	Lego WeDo 2.0	Programming, Engineering
12	UoA-ETL	Robots and walking mechanisms	LEGO Mindstorms	Programming - Engineering
13	UoA-ETL	A Robotic insect	Arduino	Engineering

The following sections present a reflective analysis of the activity plans:

MAIN OBJECTIVES

The main objectives pursued with the activities designed for the first year of the project, primarily focused on the domain of Technology and Engineering. Secondary subjects that were involved in the robotic constructions were Mathematics, Science, and Business. In fewer cases Art was mentioned and in one case it was subject related (construction of a robot painter). However, the construction of the robot painter did not actually focus on aspects of painting as the robot mainly drew coloured geometrical shapes (like lines, squares etc.) and in another case (ESI CEE) robotics was combined with creative thinking based on mind-maps. Furthermore, Language and Arts in lessons created for robotics primarily involve activities around construction – like the Engineer’s journal and not the actual robotic constructions.

MULTI-DISCIPLINARITY

Multi-disciplinarity is one of the special characteristics of robotics activities (Yiannoutsou, Nikitopoulou, Kynigos, Gueorguiev, & Fernandez, 2016) and was part of the design of the first version of the activity plans. However, with the exception of “Mathematics” and physics laws, which are seamlessly integrated, mainly in the way robot vehicles function, other domains are superficially covered. The example from art mentioned above is one example of this. Another can be found in the “Robotic insect” activity plan which makes connections with biology because it requires students to obtain some knowledge about the structure of the body of an insect but there is no need for students to do something more than recall the knowledge they already have about how insects look. Furthermore, if the structure of the body of a real insect is not correctly represented this has little impact in the final result as the main point of the task is to construct a robot which will be able to walk with more than two modular feet.

An exception to this observation is the “Crazy robots” activity plan where aspects of design, sales and marketing are very well integrated in the task and in the final design of the robot (determining materials, creating an appealing look and feel etc.).

STUDENT AGE, SETTING AND CONNECTION TO THE CURRICULUM

Student age ranged from 6 year olds to 17 year olds (for an overview of the statistics of workshops see D.2.1 section 5.1). The settings covered by the activity plans range from formal school settings where the activities are integrated to the school schedule to non-formal settings as it is the case of ECER – Conference and the preparation for ECER workshop (See sections 4.5 and 4.6). However, the activity plans describe situations where the robotics activity can be implemented in something like a grey zone: i.e. in the school in the context of extra –curricular activities which take place after school or during school hours (if there is a slot for extra-curricular activities) especially in cases of primary schools which seem to have more freedom.

Not all the activities created are connected to a formal national curriculum especially those that are designed for non-formal settings and those implemented in the context of extra – curricular school activities. Even though there are activity plans declaring connection to the curriculum, the specific concepts of the curriculum are not included in the plan. This is an issue that needs to be addressed in the next version of activity plans especially because connection to curricula in some cases is a criterion for implementing an activity in the classroom. This is not to say that activity plans should always be connected to a specific curriculum. On the contrary activity plans that are not aligned to a specific curriculum might contribute in exploring new ways of thinking and learning around robotics. Additionally, it is these connections to the curriculum that will be appealing to teachers who have limited time to review activity plans, let alone implement educational robotics activities in an often packed curriculum. This will be an important consideration to both the design of the Activity Plan, individual workshops and the repository.

CONSTRUCTIONS IN ACTIVITY PLANS

Constructions in activity plans can take the form of digital and/or physical constructions. Where activity plans focus on digital constructions, we see that they focus on constructing the behaviour of the robot through programming and in these cases the teachers provide the robot already constructed. This for example was a choice made by a UoA researcher (Making a robot “smart”) due to organizational issues (number of students, availability of robotic kits, scheduling of the activity). In other cases this might be an option if the teacher decides that robotics provide an excellent context for teaching programming and focuses the activity exactly on this aspect. In other cases the activity plan includes a visual guide for students to follow in order to create their robot or provide a semi-constructed robot where students add specific parts (like sensors). In the conference and contest preparation workshop students construct and program their own robot. Digital constructions (i.e. programs defining the robot’s behaviour) can be driven by brainstorming sessions about the tasks robots can perform (see for example section 4.3).

Some activity-plans focus on the process of constructing a robot from scratch where the morphology of the robot is a parameter influencing its behaviour. This is the case of the ECER conference. The robotic Insect is a similar case where the emphasis is on concepts of electrical engineering. An activity plan that focuses and supports with concrete steps the design process is “Crazy robots”. In this case students engage in designing and prototyping a robot. Specifically the first phase consists of a set of steps that it is based on the characteristics of robotic constructions: Robot task (assignment); Robot Interaction; Robot morphology (looks and materials); Robot behaviour; Robot parts. Prototyping simulates the design process as it is undertaken by groups with different interests and expertise: Sales and marketing group, Engineering, Human Robot Interaction group, Research and development group, Design group. This as an activity plan that it is fine-tuned to the characteristics of constructions with robotics and it has a very strong social dimension fostered by design communication and discussion between groups.

Although the Botball preparation workshop doesn’t support a specific construction, it helps students to familiarize themselves with the physical parts of Botball and with their functionalities through small tasks and examples. This seems to be a good introductory process for supporting student familiarisation with a robotic kit before the students to engage with physical constructions themselves.

TEACHING METHODS TO SUPPORT CONSTRUCTIONIST ACTIVITY

A close look at the activity plans reveals that they demonstrate an implicit methodology for supporting student constructionist activity. In some cases activity plans use one of the methods below or a variety of approaches. In addition to constructionist activities, there appear to be instances of direct instruction. Although constructionist workshops can include direct instruction, it is a fine balance which requires careful consideration and justification, with students enabled to explore and not become reliant on tutors.

INCLUDING TASKS WITH GRADUAL COMPLEXITY

Activity plans which include tasks with gradual complexity, start with simple procedures or physical constructions and in consecutive steps new elements are added in the process. For example the activity plan “Making a robot smart” includes the following programming tasks: move a robot four blocks, detect an obstacle and stop, detect and obstacle make a U- turn and move for 4 floor plates, detect an obstacle avoid it and continue to the initial route. In case of physical constructions they provide a basic construction and then students are expected to add parts (like sensors)

PROVIDING EXAMPLES FOR ANALYSIS AND HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Instead of employing direct instruction (i.e. introducing loops) to introduce a concept or explain an example, constructionist methodology might focus on providing students with an example and ask them to test it and observe the behaviour of the robot with the aim of identifying the role of specific programming concepts and structures like loops. This is a teaching and learning process which makes use of the affordances of digital constructionist environments where the observation of the generated behaviour (i.e. feedback) its analysis provide the grounds for the formulation of a hypothesis about how things work (Yiannoutsou & Mavrikis, 2012). This method is demonstrated in section 4.7 of D4.1, where students are expected to find out the role of the loop and its parameters in a program, which results in moving the robot until it detects an object at 20 cm away.

MODIFYING AND EXTENDING GIVEN EXAMPLES

Another approach encountered in the activity plans that can support student constructionist activity is for the teacher to provide a ready-made example and ask from the students to change it so that it demonstrates a slightly different behaviour. This method allows students to focus on concepts that are relevant to the specific learning objectives (white box) and without struggling with complexities that are not relevant to the specific activity plan (black box). The Educational Technology Lab of the University of Athens has developed a theoretical construct in the design of digital learning environments (technologies and learning activities) which extends the idea of modifying given examples to modifying half-baked digital constructs (Kynigos, 2007). The term “half – baked” is coined by Kynigos (ibid) to describe exploratory digital environments conceived, by design, to call for modification and change supporting targeted learning.

ARGUMENTATION, DISCUSSION AND MAKER CULTURE

Orchestration of work in the organized workshops - irrespectively of context (formal non-formal) - involved group work and whole classroom discussions. Collaborative work and sharing of ideas and constructions was a central issue: a) in the design rationale of the activity plans for robotics (see for example D.2.1 and Yiannoutsou, Nikitopoulou, Kynigos, Gueorguiev, & Fernandez, 2016) b) in the discussions with ER4STEM partners and UoA teachers regarding the implementation of the workshops c) in student reflections and d) in the evaluation of Scientix ambassadors (see section 5 of D4.1).

Specifically, before the implementation of the workshops it was suggested that teachers should include a social dimension in their design where students in the middle of the workshops should describe to other students in the same class what they have created up to the moment and what where their problems and their future plans. The same process was supposed to be repeated at the end of the process where groups should share an image of their robot, their code a short description of what their robot does. For the group of Greek teachers it was suggested to use Edmodo. Edmodo was selected for the following reasons: a) it is free b) it allows collaboration and post view among different teachers c) follows the familiar Facebook interaction of posting comments and attachments. The idea of introducing a blog to describe and present final constructions was also introduced to other ER4STEM partners through the pre-evaluation kit (D.6.1) shared among the participants for the standardization of the evaluation process. The rationale behind this suggestion was to stress the social dimension of constructions and especially to foster aspects of the maker culture where ideas are explained and shared, help is sought and advice is provided. However, an overview of the activity plans shows that although orchestration of the students involved almost exclusively group work and discussions in the classroom, the sequence of teaching activities does not include time for sharing constructions providing advice and help. Reflection also provides an opportunity for students as groups or individuals to identify what they have learned and how, making explicit what are often implicit aims in the workshops

MAIN ACTIVITIES – IN TEACHING AND LEARNING SEQUENCE

This section groups and briefly describes the activities integrated in the activity plans to support the teaching and learning process with robotics. The first version of the activity plans includes combinations of the following activities:

INTRODUCTORY ACTIVITIES

Introductory sessions usually include presentations, discussions, short hands-on activities with robots and even robot simulation activities with the students simulating the behaviour of a robot. Specifically introductory sessions might include one of or a combination of the following activities:

- Presentations might refer to: a) the task; b) aspects about robots, their uses, their design; etc. c) the robotic kit that is going to be used; d) the rules of working with robots and e) collaborating with other students and researchers.
- Presentations might be followed or replaced by discussions that develop around a central question like: what is a robot, what tasks a robot can perform, are robots part of our lives etc.
- Introductory sessions quite often, especially when they include presentation of the robotic kit, include a short hands on experimentation with the robot like making the robot move towards a specific direction, make a sound, turn etc.

An interesting introductory activity involved the simulation of the robot's behaviour. This introductory activity involves the simulation of two main roles per group of students: one student will be the robot and the rest of the group will be the designer of the robot. Specifically, the rest of the group will design a maze in which the robot-student should navigate blindfolded. The group should provide to the robot-student the directions for the navigation of the robot before entering the maze. Then the teacher uses the experience from this activity as a basis to introduce concepts related to the way robots function and the importance of robotic parts like sensors.

PROGRAMMING ORIENTED ACTIVITIES

Programming oriented activities focus on specific concepts like sequential programming, loops, event handling etc. The emphasis of these activities is on engaging students with the programming language in order for the students to be able to use the programming concepts as instruments to define the robot behaviour. Robot behaviour is used as a feedback mechanism for the students to make conjectures and refine their understanding of the programming concepts. Usually, programming activities are followed by tasks, which focus on the robot behaviour and make use of the programming concepts introduced. Examples of such activities are the following: Don't fall off the table; Going straight; Avoid crash; Trip in a corridor; Friendly pet; Bright colours; Line follower etc.

ENGINEERING AND DESIGN ORIENTED ACTIVITIES

Engineering and design oriented activities focus mainly on the robot (physical construction) and its characteristics. This set of activities might include:

- Construction of the robot using a visual guide (this is an activity suggested for beginners)
- Construction of the robot with reference to a specific morphology (e.g. construct an insect) without other help
- Play with and explore the robot's behaviour, using ready-made pieces of code
- Enhance the behaviour of a pre-constructed robot with adding new parts

Construction of the robot might be structured according to the following design activities

- Robot task (assignment)

- Robot interaction
- Robot morphology (looks and materials)
- Robot behaviour
- Robot parts

Another approach to the construction of a robot is suggested in “Crazy Robots”, where prototyping follows the actual design process of a robotic company including tasks that refer to: a) Sales and marketing; b) Engineering; c) Human Robot Interaction; d) Research and development; e) Design and f) Evaluation of the product (from the “sales department” and from the user’s perspective)

All activity plans include a combination of programming and engineering activities. The activity plan designed for the contest preparation workshop includes a nice balance of engineering and programming activities: First prototype: construct a simple robot (beginners use a guide); Programming principles - simple movements; Complex programming structures, using sensors; Experimentation with parts of a robotic kit using short assignments and examples. Similarly the conference includes a set of competitions which integrate programming and engineering activities.

EVALUATION ACTIVITIES

For the purposes of the project evaluation, this followed a standardized process regardless of the activity plan. However, evaluation activities like peer-reviewing which were expected to happen in the context of construction activities and during student’s social interaction were not documented in sufficient detail in the activity plans. Additionally there were no examples of evaluating what students had learnt in relation to the objectives or engaging with pupil voice beyond the generic evaluation kit.

Baseline questions

In this section, the results from the analysis of the activity plans in relation to the baseline questions are presented. Some questions cannot be answered based on the evidence within the activity plans, some questions can be answered in part using the activity plans and none can be answered by the activity plans on their own. However the findings from this analysis demonstrate the breadth of activities and the commonalities between them in relation to the baseline questions.

OBJECTIVE 1: ER4STEM WILL APPROACH AND ENGAGE CHILDREN BY OFFERING MULTIPLE ENTRY POINTS INTO CREATIVE STEM (STEAM) VIA ROBOTICS

ARE THERE MULTIPLE ENTRY POINTS FACILITATED THROUGH THE ER4STEM FRAMEWORK?

Analysis of the activity plans identified a number of entry points to robotics:

Exploratory Introduction (Goal and non-goal orientated): Several focus around the construction and/or programming of robots for the first time as an introduction to robots and what they can do. They often include short tasks, challenges or puzzles to be completed to guide students in their exploration and could be characterized as an exploratory introduction to robots. Other introductory workshops begin with a specific challenge which is connected to a topic beyond robotics, which results in a similarly structured exploration of the potential of robots. Some of the related activity plans positions the student as a scientist, for example “Making a Robot Smart”. In this sense we could

consider that these activity plans provide multiple entry points which are closely related to an interest in robots and science.

Set challenges: Beyond general exploratory introductions, set challenges are found in a range of activity plans. Sometimes these are open challenges, with a single goal which students need to complete in any way they wish, at other times students are provided with a series of smaller challenges after which they should be able to complete the main challenge. A typical example of a set challenge is “find the exit in any given maze”. There is no flexibility in this challenge and there are typically limited opportunities for the task to be connected to personal interests.

Challenges linked to stories: A particular variation on the set ‘solve a maze’ challenge is one which is linked to a fictional story or context. For example in “My first robot” students are given a set task – moving a robot in an unfriendly environment. This asks them to draw on their imagination and provides opportunities for creativity beyond the set task.

Challenges connected to everyday experiences (authentic challenges): In the “Robotic Safe Swing and Seesaw” students are presented with a challenge which is connected to an everyday experience, in this case playing on swings and seesaws. However the description of the sequence of activities does not provide sufficient information to understand how the topic of the “safe swing and seesaw” is unpacked and if this analysis can provide multiple entry points to the students participating in the workshop. Furthermore, this activity plan shares certain similarities with “Crazy Robots” which, although potentially providing multiple entry points, there is no explicit adaptation to the context so that they fit the topic of the activity plan (i.e. the construction of a “safe swing and seesaw”). Thus there are unanswerable questions like: how autonomous actions of robots are connected to the “safe swing and seesaw”; how designs based on student imaginations where “their robot makes everything they want” is extended to fit the construction of a “safe swing and seesaw”.

Open creative expression: One of the workshops integrates art through the generation of interesting drawings through programming. Although this could at times be viewed as constrained rather than open creativity there continues to be opportunities for open expression. In this specific example, “constructing and controlling a robot painter”, students use loops to draw a square and then programme the robot to use multiple coloured pens to create an abstract drawing.

Vehicle for learning: One of the proposed advantages of robotics is that it draws on a range of subject matter and provides opportunities for students to explore, test and extend their understanding of these subjects through the creation and programming of robots. Yet, across the activity plans we see limited curriculum links and those which are there are typically vague. However “Robots and walking mechanisms” provides an example of students engaging in research to understand the walking mechanisms of humans and animals in order to design a solution for walking robots. Here students are applying what they have learned to the creation of a robot. This vehicle for learning is also an example of a set challenge.

Overall we see that challenges set by the teacher or tutor are the most common ways for students to first engage in educational robotics activities. While some of these relate to creative elements or are used as a vehicle to engage with curriculum content, this is unusual. Further consideration is needed of the types of entry points that could be facilitated through the ER4STEM framework, particularly to leverage the creative opportunities of working with robots and provide more opportunities for students to direct their own learning.

DO THE ACTIVITIES ALLOW LEARNERS TO CONNECT ROBOTS TO THEIR PERSONAL INTERESTS?

Typically the description of activities within the activity plans do not provide evidence to suggest that the activities allow learners to connect robots to their personal interests. There are only two types of activity plans which suggest a link. One is the topic of the activity plan “Robotic safe swing and seesaw” which addresses primary school students. In this activity plan students can draw from their personal experience and everyday life when engaged with the specific activity. The other is the design of the activity plan “A robotic insect” which is designed for students of vocational education. The activity plan makes a good mapping with students’ professional interests (i.e. programmers and electrical engineers) as those students are personally interested in robots and circuits.

DO CHILDREN SHARE THEIR IDEAS WITH/THROUGH THESE TANGIBLE ARTEFACTS?

The activity plans are all designed for students to work in small groups and the assumption is that they will share their ideas within the group. However the way that this is facilitated is not explicitly stated. Additionally some activity plans refer to the students presenting their ideas but this is often not explained in the sequence of activities.

There is an exception in two activity plans: “Solving the maze problem with Lego EV3” “Robots and walking mechanisms”. In the first activity plan there were designed two activities: one was called experimentation and the other was called performance. In the first activity students expected to experiment with their constructions and exchange ideas with other groups about how they constructed their robot. In the activity called performance, each group was expected to present their robot solving the maze problem and explain how they programmed it. In the second activity plan, the teacher designed an activity where groups were supposed to test the robots constructed by other groups and provide feedback.

DO THEY LEARN BASIC SCIENTIFIC CONCEPTS?

While some activity plans state within the objectives that students will engage with scientific concepts, such as angles or loops, typically they are not directly referred to in the rest of the activity plan. Some objectives are presented at a much higher level, suggesting that students will engage with mathematics, for example. Therefore, while students may learn scientific concepts, this may not be due to the design of the workshop and instead appears to be an unplanned by-product.

Concepts most typically referred to appear within the domains of computer science/programming, engineering and mathematics. In one of the workshops there is reference to biological concepts around walking mechanisms and insect body structure, however existing knowledge is sufficient to complete the tasks.

OBJECTIVE 2: ER4STEM WILL OFFER EDUCATIONAL METHODS FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS TO ENGAGE ALL YOUNG LEARNERS

Many questions within this objective cannot be answered using the activity plan. Where this is the case a brief statement to this effect is made.

DO THE ACTIVITIES ENCOURAGE INTEREST IN STEM EDUCATION?

There is no explicit connection within the activity plans to encouraging an interest in STEM education.

DO THE ACTIVITIES ENCOURAGE INTEREST IN STEM CAREERS?

Similarly to the previous question, there is no explicit connection within the activity plans to encouraging interest in STEM careers. However some activity plans include a discussion on the work of scientists. For example, one activity plan uses the introduction to engage learners in this discussion and make explicit the relationship between robotics and science. By putting students in the role of scientists we could consider that this activity could encourage interest in STEM education and careers, however this requires supporting evidence from other sources.

DO THE APPROACHES/ACTIVITIES APPEAL TO GIRLS?

Across the activity plans there is no evidence to suggest that the approaches or activities have been altered to appeal to girls. However, as previously mentioned, some of the entry points and activities favour boys. The robot painter workshop and robot swing and seesaw are two workshops that could be viewed as gender neutral and therefore could appeal to girls as much as boys.

DO GIRLS ENGAGE WITH CHALLENGES OR LET BOYS ‘TAKE OVER’?

None of the activity plans detail how these situations could be mitigated.

ARE GIRLS INTERESTED IN THE STEM TOPICS?

Again there is no evidence that the activity plans have been designed to take this into account.

ARE POPULAR GENDER STEREOTYPES HELD? ARE THEY CHANGED?

There is no evidence in the activity plans that the activities are designed to address popular stereotypes.

DID THEY PARTICIPATE IN COLLABORATIVE WORK?

As previously mentioned, although all activity plans required students to work in groups, they typically provided insufficient information on the orchestration of the group work to know whether collaboration was intended. Collaboration suggests that students should be working together to solve problems, rather than working separately within the same group. However, on the basis of the activity plans there appear to be assumptions that students know how to engage in collaborative work.

The only workshops where there was some clear orchestration of collaboration was the Lego EV3 and robot walking mechanism workshops implemented in Greece. There are two activities which mention explicitly collaborative work: one is called experimentation where intra-group communication about robot constructions is encouraged; the other is called “Performance” where each group present their robot moving in the maze and they explain how they programmed the robot behaviour.

WERE THOSE WHO WERE NOT INTERESTED IN STEM INSPIRED BY THEIR PEERS?

There is no evidence in the activity plans that the workshops were designed to provide opportunities for this beyond the fact that students were working in groups. If it occurred it is likely to be serendipitous, rather than planned.

OBJECTIVE 3: ER4STEM WILL STUDY REAL-WORLD SOCIETAL PROBLEMS AS PERCEIVED BY EACH CHILD AND RELATE SOCIETAL CHALLENGES TO EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES AND REQUIRED INNOVATIONS

DID CHILDREN IDENTIFY AND DEFINE PROBLEMS THAT INFLUENCE THEIR LIVES?

Of those activities that had the potential to allow students to identify and define their own problems, few could be related to influencing their own lives. One which could was the activity “Robotic safe swing and seesaw”, opportunities to discuss the topic of safety in a playground and how robots could help. However there is no evidence in the activity plan that there was an explicit design supporting children to identify and define such problems.

Introductory discussions on the role of robots do provide opportunities for students to identify and define problems that influence their lives that robots could help them to solve and in the Bulgarian case study presented earlier, the creativity session provides another route through brainstorming and discussion.

WERE THEY EQUIPPED WITH THE NECESSARY SKILLS TO SOLVE THESE?

Workshops which introduced students to creative thinking provided students with useful skills to brainstorm potential solutions. However across workshops there were few or no opportunities to begin the development of such robots as these activities were typically framed as an introduction to robots before turning attention to the main workshop activity.

DO THEY HAVE AN OPPORTUNITY TO PRESENT THEIR IDEAS AND ARTEFACTS TO EACH OTHER AS ‘PROPER’ SCIENTISTS?

Referring to the earlier question on sharing their ideas through the artefacts that they created, there were limited opportunities for students to do this outside of the competition which has an associated conference at which students present their ideas in a formal setting as ‘proper’ scientists. This type of activity may have been particularly relevant to the “robots and walking mechanisms” and similar workshops which require students to conduct some research before attempting to solve a given problem, however there was no evidence of this in the activity plan.

The “Robots and walking mechanisms” activity plan included a phase where students were expected to exchange ideas with other groups about their constructions and all groups were implicitly expected to discuss and share their ideas with their peers in the context of their work as a group.

DO THEY DEVELOP ‘SOFT-SKILLS’?

A variety of ‘soft-skills’ are referred to in the activity plans, including teamwork, listening, communication with others, presenting, problem identification and solving, taking roles, and

creativity. Except for some opportunities for brainstorming already described, there is no evidence beyond the objectives that these skills have been designed for. As with collaboration, it appears that any development of these skills would be a possible by-product of engaging in the workshop, rather than planned for.

DO THEY LEARN INTRARELATIONAL (HOW WELL THEY KNOW THEMSELVES) AND INTERPERSONAL SKILLS?

There are no opportunities to develop intrarelatational skills in the activity plans. Beyond collaboration and teamwork, there is no evidence to suggest that the development of interpersonal skills is considered in the activity plans beyond so-called 'soft-skills' objectives.

Unexpected findings:

Here four unexpected findings which emerged from the analysis of the activity plans are briefly presented:

- Activity plan: "Making a robot smart": The specific activity plan had described explicitly a methodology for constructionist learning where the design for introducing new knowledge to the students involved analysing, testing, altering and extending specific examples.
- Activity plan: "My first Robot": it is the only activity plan that focuses on student attitude towards knowledge and in supporting them to formulate a methodology to make the impossible possible. So, in the introductory session the teacher shows the students a fully functional robot and tells the students that he expects from them to do the same aiming to make them feel that this is impossible for them. The ultimate stated purpose is to help students realise that the impossible becomes possible with hard work and collaboration.
- Activity plan: "Robots and walking mechanisms" The interesting aspect in this activity plan is the emphasis on the design process: improving initial solutions, following an iterative process. This is interesting because it challenges the concept of right and wrong solution and makes students familiar with the process of improving initial solutions.
- Activity plan "A robotic insect": The interesting characteristic of this activity plan is that by design facilitates multiple entry points for students of vocational education with different expertise. This means that the activity in order to be completed requires the expertise of the electrical engineers and the expertise of programmers. If the activity addressed only electrical engineers then the activity plan would provide the programming part of the activity ready or almost ready and vice versa.

6.2 DRAW-A-SCIENTIST

In order to answer the questions "are popular gender stereotypes held?" and "are they changed?", it is important to assess what stereotypes are held by children. Rather than giving students a tick list of stereotypes, or a Likert scale questionnaire, the Draw-A-Scientist activity allows students to creatively express their concept of a scientist in an easily sharable form. This prevents the students' responses from being filtered by adult assumptions and the difficulties of using the written language to express something complex and nuanced.

Beyond whether women or men could be scientists, this activity also allows analysis of the types of things that children associate with being a scientist. This may be physical characteristics of the scientist, the type of place that they work, the things that they interact with or the events that may

happen. This is important because gender stereotypes are more complex than whether women and/or men can do a particular job. It also allows us to consider the types of activities within those jobs that students associate male or female scientists with, which may influence their interest in perusing STEM subjects and future careers.

In this instance of the activity, students were also invited to write a description or add annotations to their drawings. This additional information aided data analysis when drawings were unclear and provided further data on the stereotypes held.

The data shows that both male and female students are more likely to draw a male scientist than a female scientist. Younger children are more likely to draw a scientist which appears to be a “mad scientist” (Figure 11) or “Einstein” character with hair on end, possibly following an explosion.

Figure 11 A mad scientist

Younger children are also more likely to draw a fantasy setting, with zombies or Frankenstein’s monster. Scientists were also more likely to be associated with “evil” or “scary” activities. This suggests that there is an influence from popular culture which is particularly influential in younger children’s perceptions of scientists.

Figure 12 A normal person

By comparison, older children are more likely to draw a scientist that “looks like a normal person”, (Figure 12) works with a computer and solves important problems. However older children were also more likely to express extreme views on scientists. For example, the image below (Figure 13 A “smartarse” scientist) was created by a 13 year-old girl who described the scientist as having no friends, hates people, had no childhood and a smartarse.

These drawings are also important when we come to consider questions about whether the workshop activities are appealing to girls, whether they have inherent gender bias and whether and how these might influence some students more than others.

Figure 13 A “smartarse” scientist

Perhaps unexpectedly, a higher number of pictures included robots. This is to be expected given the fact that most students were told before the activity that they were going to be learning about robots and are likely to have made the association with scientists for themselves. Others with this information may have recalled seeing scientists in cartoons (for example) working on robots. However, by comparison to the wider literature which uses Draw-A-Scientist, this is unusual. Therefore it could be suggested that this activity makes some initial connections between the work of scientists and those working in STEM more generally. For example, one female student drew a female scientist with spanners, which could be interpreted as an engineer (Figure 14).

Figure 14 A female engineer

One important limitation of this data comes from the translation of evaluation materials from English to the partner languages. “Draw a scientist” in English is gender neutral, however in German and Bulgarian ‘scientist’ is a masculine word. While there are female forms used to explicitly refer to a female scientist or a scientist who is female, they are used only in this context. While gender neutral forms have been created, young children tend to be less familiar with the word as it is not in common use. Therefore in some contexts the task could be inferred to mean, draw a male scientist and therefore it is unclear whether the gender bias seen in the results has been influenced by the phrasing of the task.

This issue was identified by partners during the year 1 data collection, by which point some partners had already collected data. So while some activities were presented as draw a male or female scientist, some are not. Also, by providing both forms, ‘male’ is privileged as first. This has implications for future data collection and the results that can be drawn from this data. Other forms of data collection are less structured or are not intended to examine gendered dimensions and therefore there are no issues with this data.

7 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings draws together evidence from each of the three phases of analysis. The discussion is kept brief as the evidence has been presented above. The result of this discussion is a series of recommendations for the development of the project in year 2, informed by the evidence from year 1.

The discussion begins by formulating answers to the baseline questions, followed by the criteria for assessing the Framework and ends with some broader issues which are emerging from the data.

7.1 BASELINE DATA

Objective 1: ER4STEM will approach and engage children by offering multiple entry points into creative STEM (STEAM) via robotics

ARE THERE MULTIPLE ENTRY POINTS FACILITATED THROUGH THE ER4STEM FRAMEWORK?

Overall we see that challenges set by the teacher or tutor are the most common ways for students to first engage in educational robotics activities. While some of these relate to creative elements or are used as a vehicle to engage with curriculum content, this is unusual. Further consideration is needed of the types of entry points that could be facilitated through the ER4STEM framework, particularly to leverage the creative opportunities of working with robots and provide more opportunities for students to direct their own learning.

The recommendation from this is that as a consortium we need to consider alternative entry points in the design of our workshops and that the Framework and Activity Plan need to provide clear guidance.

DO THE ACTIVITIES ALLOW LEARNERS TO CONNECT ROBOTS TO THEIR PERSONAL INTERESTS?

Currently we can see that the activities do not allow learners to connect robots to their personal interests. Typically the description of activities within the activity plans do not provide evidence to suggest that the activities allow learners to connect robots to their personal interests. Although evidence from the interviews tentatively suggest that learners make connections for themselves, realising that robots helped them to understand how science is integrated in things in their everyday lives; there is no evidence to suggest that the learners are making choices within the activities to connect to personal interests. This is most likely due to the fact that the activities focus on set challenges identified and set by the tutors in advance. Although some of these challenges are open and exploratory, they do not allow for the students to identify their own challenges or alter the challenge to suit their personal interests.

Another reason may be the limited opportunities to link activities to students' personal experiences. One exception to this is the "Robotic safe swing and seesaw" activity, which allows them to use information gained from this experience and to engage in a construction that could have applications in their everyday life. Furthermore, the topic of this activity is more gender neutral by comparison to

other activities that focus on vehicles which are considered more “boy-friendly”. However there is no explicit reference in the activity plan description for a design attempting to meet various personal interests of the students.

The gendering of activities is important when we consider that the findings of the Draw-A-Scientist task show that a scientist is most likely to be represented as male, regardless of whether the child is male or female. The lack of female scientists in popular media, from cartoons to documentaries is often associated with limited identification of women as scientists and aspiration to become a scientist by young girls and women who do not see someone who represents them or that they would aspire to become. A similar concern exists around the types of activities and relates to the limited entry points. However this does not mean that we should introduce the ‘pinkification’ of robotics. Instead it means that the Framework and Activity Plans need to consider how all children can be engaged in robotics activities. One route to this may be providing more opportunities for learners to connect robots to their personal interests within the activity plans and making this explicit.

DO CHILDREN SHARE THEIR IDEAS WITH/THROUGH THESE TANGIBLE ARTEFACTS?

The activity plans are all designed for students to work in small groups and the assumption is that they will share their ideas within the group. However the way that this is facilitated is not explicitly stated. Additionally some activity plans refer to the students presenting their ideas but this is often not explained in the sequence of activities.

From the observational data, we can see many instances of students physically moving robots as they try to explain something to other students, or showing a programme on the screen before watching the robot implement the programme and then discussing changes to the programme afterwards. A particularly powerful set of data in this respect comes from the focus group at the Botball competition who carried with them a GoPro camera. There were multiple instances across the competition days where the students would try to explain something to each other and physically manipulate the robot to assist them.

When we consider the literature on robotics in education, we see that the physical manipulation of robots as an object to think or communicate with is a common feature. This is associated with the social-constructivist learning and the experiential learning cycle, in which abstract ideas, once made concrete can easily be observed, shared and discussed.

DO THEY LEARN BASIC SCIENTIFIC CONCEPTS?

While some activity plans state within the objectives that students will engage with scientific concepts, such as angles or loops, typically they are not directly referred to in the rest of the activity plan. Some objectives are presented at a much higher level, suggesting that students will engage with mathematics, for example. Therefore, while students may learn scientific concepts, this may not be due to the design of the workshop and instead appears to be an unplanned by-product.

Examining the responses of children across the data, we see that while they can identify that they have learned things from the workshop, they are not necessarily related to the objectives of the workshop. This is problematic as it casts doubt on whether the workshop and activity plan are fit for purpose, whether their learning is serendipitous and whether it could have occurred just as effectively (or more so) without a robotics activity. This is true for both scientific concepts and soft-skills, which are discussed later.

DISCUSSION

Overall we can see from the evidence presented in this report that there are limited routes to engaging children in STE(A)M through robotics. The tendency is to focus on highly structured and pre-defined activities which take a task-and-finish approach, rather than allowing learners to explore, test and extend their understanding in personally meaningful contexts. There are also issues around what is learned, when comparing activity plans and the results of the workshop from the student perspective.

From this analysis there are clear recommendations for the development of the Framework, Activity Plans and implementation of workshops in Year 2 in order for the objective to be met and for valuable opportunities for learning to be identified.

Objective 2: ER4STEM will offer educational methods for educational robotics to engage all young learners

DO THE ACTIVITIES ENCOURAGE INTEREST IN STEM EDUCATION AND CAREERS?

For the purpose of this discussion, future intentions around careers and education are brought together. On the whole we can see that the current workshop activities do not necessarily encourage an interest in STEM education and careers. However this is some tentative evidence to suggest that some students who have a low sense of self-efficacy before the workshop in science and maths, begin to develop some confidence in these areas.

Here we are looking for an attitudinal change at the end of what might be only an 8 hour workshop. In this context we would expect an increase interest to be temporary and largely mediated by their day-to-day experiences. Although it is beyond the scope of the project, the longer-term integration of these activities would be required before any clear answers can be given for this question.

Years 2 and 3 of the project will, however present an opportunity to engage with students who have participated in the workshops in year 1. Given the same participant identifiers, they could be tracked over several years to provide more evidence. This is currently beyond the scope of the project but may be considered in the future.

It is also worth noting that there is some tentatively positive evidence in relation to the careers that children say they would like to pursue, between the pre- and post-workshop questionnaires. An example of this is provided in the Bulgarian case study, however a counter example is found in the Maltese case study. It is interesting to note that in the Bulgarian workshop there was a brainstorming activity which may have influenced this and children were clearly aware of the potential role of robots in future careers which were unrelated to STEM. While no firm conclusions can be drawn, it will be valuable to note whether workshops which are informed by the Framework in Years 2 and 3 of the project have a more, less or equally positive effect on this trend.

DO THE APPROACHES/ACTIVITIES APPEAL TO GIRLS?

Across the activity plans there is no evidence to suggest that the approaches or activities have been altered to appeal to girls. However, as previously mentioned, some of the entry points and activities may favour boys as they are based on cars or tanks and competition. The robot painter workshop

and robot swing and seesaw are two workshops that could be viewed as gender neutral and therefore could appeal to girls as much as boys. Interestingly, the activity plan “Robots and walking mechanisms” was implemented with 14 boys and only one girl. In this workshop participation in the activity was on a voluntary basis whereas the other workshops were implemented in the context of normal curriculum.

This raises the importance, not only of the entry point and activity, but also the social orchestration. As noted in both the Bulgarian and Maltese case studies, there were challenges for those working in mixed-gender groups. The Maltese data clearly shows that in one instance the girl in the video is engaged whilst the boy is disengaged, whilst in the Bulgarian we see evidence of the opposite, so this is not necessarily a one-directional effect and may perhaps be on a continuum, related to a range of factors. We currently have insufficient evidence to draw any firm conclusions on this.

Another factor that should be considered is the difficulty and ‘fun factor’ of each activity for each student. While the evidence clearly shows that some students enjoyed the activities, even though they were perceived as difficult, there are concerns when students tend to find the activities too difficult or too easy. The concepts of ‘Hard Fun’ and ‘Flow’ are important here. While Papert identified that activities which ‘work’ are both hard and fun, Csikszentmihalyi’s (1990) concept of Flow suggests that if activities are too easy or too difficult, in relation to their existing knowledge and skills, people are more likely to disengage and give up. This is often used in game design and should be considered in activity design, however it is complex and needs to take account of individual learners. When workshops are implemented by anyone other than a regular class teacher, we cannot expect them to have this knowledge of the students. One approach to address this is the differentiation of activities. This could be through more or less scaffolds to support different aspects of the learning activity, extended challenges and of course amounts and type of tutor input.

DO GIRLS ENGAGE WITH CHALLENGES OR LET BOYS ‘TAKE OVER’?

There is evidence across workshops that in mixed gender teams boys are more likely to ‘take over’. Girls challenge the boys’ dominance using various tactics, including gaining support from the teacher and getting the teacher to challenge the boys’ behaviour; as well as working independently from the boys to ‘prove’ themselves. These types of activities often go unchallenged by adults and while girls are praised for showing the boys that they are ‘good enough’, boys are rarely admonished. Activity plans do not identify how these situations could be mitigated if they occur.

This aligns with evidence on gender stereotypes, where we see that both boys and girls are more likely to consider a scientist to be male than female. Similarly in the data we see girls going to female tutors for help with team issues and men for technical issues. We also find evidence of both boys and girls looking to show-off and discuss what they are doing with male tutors than female tutors. However there is insufficient evidence to make any definitive statements.

If ER4STEM is to meet the second objective, it needs to find approaches to the social orchestration of group work that takes into account these challenges. Rather than targeting girls or boys with specific actions, a more equitable approach would be to provide all teams with guidance on how they should interact, whether in single or mixed gender groups. In years 2 and 3 of the project, evidence will need to be collected to see if this is being achieved.

ARE GIRLS INTERESTED IN THE STEM TOPICS?

Analysis of the activity plans shows that there is little evidence of STEM topics being overtly presented to students and therefore it is not possible to answer this question at this time. Where girls have a choice with regards to participation, girls do not appear to be interested - the activity plan “Robots and walking mechanisms” was implemented with 14 boys and only one girl. However, without evidence on past experiences of robotics workshops by those who did and did not choose to participate, we cannot say that educational robotics had any effect in this situation.

ARE POPULAR GENDER STEREOTYPES HELD? ARE THEY CHANGED?

Evidence from the Draw-A-Scientist activity, video observations and tutor reflections demonstrate that popular gender stereotypes are held. However there is limited evidence to suggest that these are changed. This is a complex and multi-faceted issue which is strongly related to the earlier questions within this objective.

DID THEY PARTICIPATE IN COLLABORATIVE WORK?

Across the workshops and data sets there is evidence that students worked in teams, as planned and that they typically worked together. However there were also instances of collaborations breaking down or being difficult to start. Additionally, two or more students may be working on the same project but working independently of each other, or only working with specific members of their team.

Without detailed knowledge of the planned social orchestration of the workshops it is difficult to draw out any further conclusions. This point will be picked up again in the discussion on teamwork.

WERE THOSE WHO WERE NOT INTERESTED IN STEM INSPIRED BY THEIR PEERS?

There is no evidence in the activity plans that the workshops were designed to provide opportunities for this beyond the fact that students were working in groups. Similarly there is no evidence from the wider workshop data sets.

From the ECER conference presentations and Botball competition we can see that students can be inspired by their peers. Typically in the competition this occurs when students are able to freely move between groups and share what they are working on or have completed. For example, the focus group at the Botball competition stated that watching other teams compete inspired them, showing them what was possible. They also found it valuable to learn that some of the top teams had been involved in the competition for several years, as they had only limited recent experience of robotics and programming. It is also worth noting that this was an all-girl team and their interactions were with mostly all-male teams but also some mixed-gender teams, with all-male teams expressing how impressed they were that they had been able to achieve so much in so little time and encouraging them to continue. This freedom of movement, discussion and observation is difficult to orchestrate in short once-off workshops and will be an important consideration going forward. Although these students were inspired, they were also pre-disposed to be interested and had already demonstrated an interest by choosing to participate in the Botball competition and conference.

DISCUSSION

From the evidence above there is the potential for a clearly gendered dimension to the design of activities and social orchestration which needs to be avoided in order for all students to be engaged. Similarly there is a need for differentiation to maintain this engagement across ability and experience levels. On point that cuts across all of these questions is that past experiences with programming and robotics have an influence on learner engagement and this is something to consider in both differentiation of activities and social orchestration.

Objective 3: ER4STEM will study real-world societal problems as perceived by each child and relate societal challenges to existing technologies and required innovations

DID CHILDREN IDENTIFY AND DEFINE PROBLEMS THAT INFLUENCE THEIR LIVES?

Of those activities that had the potential to allow students to identify and define their own problems, few could be related to influencing their own lives. One which could was the activity “Robotic safe swing and seesaw”, opportunities to discuss the topic of safety in a playground and how robots could help. However there is no evidence in the activity plan that there was an explicit design supporting children to identify and define such problems.

Introductory discussions on the role of robots do provide opportunities for students to identify and define problems that influence their lives that robots could help them to solve and in the Bulgarian case study presented earlier, the creativity session provides another route through brainstorming and discussion.

WERE THEY EQUIPPED WITH THE NECESSARY SKILLS TO SOLVE THESE?

Workshops which introduced students to creative thinking provided students with useful skills to brainstorm potential solutions. However across workshops there were few or no opportunities to begin the development of such robots as these activities were typically framed as an introduction to robots before turning attention to the main workshop activity.

Although activity plans were typically not designed to allow students the opportunity to solve problems that they identified, it is clear that some of the workshops equipped learners with valuable skills that contribute to solving these problems. For example, in the Bulgarian case study the introduction of brainstorming begins to equip students with the ability to creatively think of potential solutions. As with teamwork, there are often assumptions that students know how to be creative, however typical school curricula and assessment are focused on the learning and reproduction of an established set of knowledge and so teaching tends to move away from rich learning experiences which involve exploration, knowledge construction and creativity towards streamlined transmission. Therefore educational robotics and the ER4STEM Framework have the potential to introduce and develop skills such as team work and creative problem solving which will be necessary to solve complex problems in the future.

DO THEY DEVELOP 'SOFT-SKILLS'?

A variety of 'soft-skills' are referred to in the activity plans, including teamwork, listening, communication with others, presenting, problem identification and solving, taking roles, and creativity. Except for some opportunities for brainstorming already described, there is no evidence beyond the objectives that these skills have been designed for. As with collaboration, it appears that any development of these skills would be a possible by-product of engaging in the workshop, rather than planned for.

Examining the responses of children across the data, we see that while they can identify that they have learned things from the workshop, they are not necessarily related to the objectives of the workshop. This is problematic as it casts doubt on whether the workshop and activity plan are fit for purpose, whether their learning is serendipitous and whether it could have occurred just as effectively (or more so) without a robotics activity. This is true for both scientific concepts and soft-skills, which are discussed later.

DO THEY LEARN INTRARELATIONAL (HOW WELL THEY KNOW THEMSELVES) AND INTERPERSONAL SKILLS?

There are no opportunities to develop intrarelatational skills in the activity plans. However some of the reflective accounts do show some awareness of themselves as part of the activity. To develop this requires engagement within each workshop, through structured activities.

For the purpose of this report and going forward with the project, 'soft-skills' are used as a container for interpersonal skills as there is significant overlap.

DISCUSSION

This objective has two clear sub-objectives. The first focuses on the ability to identify and define problems that are of relevance to children's every-day lives and the skills to solve these problems, while the second relates to soft-skills. Both require what are known as 21st Century skills, and these will be discussed further in the following sections.

7.2 EVALUATION CRITERIA

The following criteria were identified in the initial proposal as areas for focus in the evaluation the ER4STEM Framework. Although the Framework was in development during year 1, and therefore could not be evaluated, the workshops in year 1 provided an opportunity to pilot the evaluation pre-kit to assess whether it met the requirements. Below is a brief discussion of the conclusions that can be drawn from the evidence presented above.

Learner engagement

On the whole, learner engagement is high across workshops. However it is not clear to what extent the children are engaged in learning, as discussed above.

Changing & sustaining attitudes to STEM

We can see that there is some limited evidence to show that without the influence of the ER4STEM framework that educational robotics activities have the potential to change or sustain attitudes to STEM.

Connecting STEM to society

There are few opportunities within the workshop activity plans for learners to connect STEM subjects and knowledge to societal issues. This is one aspect for consideration in the development of the Framework and Activity Plans.

Creativity and Entrepreneurial activity

Within the design of most workshops there were limited opportunities for students to develop and express their creativity. There were no opportunities to develop entrepreneurial skills through related activities. However, we might consider that without creativity, entrepreneurship is difficult and so needs to be developed or at least explicitly engaged with first.

Collaborative working

In all workshops, students worked in teams, usually consisted of 3-4 members. In the most cases they had a good collaboration in their team, though there were some incidents that they faced some collaboration problems as mentioned on the tutor's reflection. As came of the data analysis, students mostly worked in two ways in their team. Either they distributed roles and they formed smaller sub-teams to focus on different parts of the activity or they worked altogether on the same task. However this is often without any clear rationale and where teams had difficulties working with each other, these ad-hoc solutions were ineffective. There are known strategies for effective collaborative working and this is a skill which needs to be developed in students, particularly where there are dysfunctional teams.

Specific tools

During Year 1 the development of Hedgehog and SLurtles was ongoing. There will be opportunities to look specifically at the workshops using these tools in the following years.

Evaluate teacher use of ER repository

At this point the repository has not been created and so this cannot be commented on.

What works, for whom and in what circumstances?

At this point we do not know what works, for whom and in what circumstances. However we are beginning to have some sense of what works for most but doesn't work for some and whom those 'some' tend to be. For example, there is clear evidence that mixed-gender groups are more likely to struggle to work as a team and collaborate effectively. Therefore ER4STEM needs to provide suitable supports for all learners so that they can work in any group and develop interpersonal skills that can be applied in any context.

Similarly we can see that whilst most students enjoy the workshops, there is limited evidence as to what they learned. To address this, clear objectives need to be stated in the activity plans, with clear opportunities for learners to engage with and achieve these objectives. Once we can measure whether or not students have engaged and achieved these outcomes, we can begin to consider what works in the context of learning, for whom and in what setting.

Associated with this is the need for differentiation, discussed above. Students' ability to complete all or a sub-set of tasks, in relation to their group composition, past experiences and existing attitudes will allow us to begin to identify what types of activities work, for whom and in what circumstances.

Pedagogic praxis also needs to be considered, including the role of the tutor as they work with different groups and how they will support learning. Consideration of this in the Activity Plan in advance of the workshop should lead tutors to have greater awareness of the approaches that they use in different situations and a growing awareness will allow them to identify for themselves what works.

Plans for further development of activities

It is anticipated that once this report and D4.1 are shared and discussed with partners in preparation for the start of Year 2 in the project meeting, that all activity plans will be developed and new opportunities will be identified.

One important development to note is that the ECER conference and Botball competition which has been run for several years in Austria will now move to Bulgaria, thanks to the development of the project consortium and ER4STEM project. Although this may reduce the number of entrants from Austria, it is hoped that this will open up the competition to more students and promote it as a truly European event for all young people

7.3 21ST CENTURY SKILLS/INDUSTRY SKILLS

While not explicitly evaluated in the first year of the project, the development of industry skills through the ER4STEM project is an anticipated outcome. These tend to encompass the previously referred to 'soft-skills' and therefore provide a more efficient unit of analysis in the future. Through the following discussion it is clear that 21st Century/industry skills need to be a key part of the ER4STEM Framework and project activities moving forward.

21st Century Skills is a popular buzz word for which it is difficult to pin-down a clear definition. In this project we refer to the importance of developing industry skills but again these are ill defined and there is a lot of expected overlap with the types of skills mentioned in definitions of 21st Century skills. Amongst the skills that students need to develop are creativity, critical thinking, collaboration and communication (see P21 as an example).

As Rotherham and Willingham (Rotherham, A. J., & Willingham, D. T. (2010). "21st-Century" Skills. *American Educator*, 17) note, so-called 21st Century skills are not 'new' but they are in more demand by society. However they are difficult to teach as they are often positioned outside the formal curriculum. At the extreme there are suggestions that with 21st Century skills, the teaching of content is not necessary. But as they do not have a curriculum of their own, teachers find them difficult to

integrate when there is a formally assessed and detailed curriculum that they must make sure their students have learnt, as this is what currently constitutes success in most countries. There is no extrinsic pressure on teachers to teach these skills and as a result children's engagement with these skills is patchy.

This project postulates that educational robotics provides an opportunity for students to engage with both 21st Century skills and curriculum content, with one requiring the other in order to be successful in this domain.

The evaluation of the first year workshops shows that it is often clear from the activity plans and artefacts of learning the extent to which children are enabled to engage in creative activities and the extent to which they do so. If there are designed-for opportunities and students are signposted to these, encouraged and supported, then we are likely to see some creativity. Heavily structured activities typically do not allow for meaningful creativity to take place. However we see elements in what might be more suitably be described as 'playfulness' in such tasks, for example the girls in the Bulgarian case study who taught their robot to say that they were its best friends. Innovation is another often mentioned 21st Century skill, closely associated with creativity. However without creativity, students are unlikely to demonstrate innovation.

Instances of creativity are typically much easier to identify in the artefacts that children create and the processes that they engage in, as opposed to what they say after the event. For this reason the artefacts of learning (both during the process and at the end), videos which show the processes students engage in and their reflections on the process are essential to understand 'what works'.

Critical thinking involves a range of skills which include conceptualising, applying, analysing, synthesising, evaluating and decision making. Moving from the abstract to the concrete and back to the abstract requires various tools to support the process, including language to discuss and record and objects to observe. In educational robotics workshops we can find evidence of students observing and discussing as part of the concrete process, which makes educational robotics well suited to developing critical thinking. What we are unable to observe is the more abstract decision making process. At times students will 'think aloud', particularly in groups, however it is very difficult to record these episodes in noisy classrooms.

Reflection is a key part of critical thinking and provides us with one route to understand the abstract parts of critical thinking, specifically decision making. But not only does it allow us insight into the mind of the learner, it also allows the learner to engage in critical thinking through critical reflection, stepping-back and considering (often for the first time) why they took the actions that they did. This opens up opportunities for learning beyond the content knowledge, in particular it provides opportunities to engage and demonstrate intrapersonal skills as well as enabling them to actively engage in the process of more generally developing 21st Century skills.

Although reflection is a key component of developing 21st Century skills, just like the skills themselves, reflection is typically not taught in schools. So it is perhaps unsurprising that while there were tools within the pre-kit to encourage reflection, the evidence shows that the reflections were typically at a surface level, describing what had happened. While this was less common with older children, they still tended to provide short answers with little or no rationale.

Educational robotics has the potential to provide children with a vehicle to engage in critical reflection in new ways. As Papert states (n.d.), robotics has 'writability'. Children enjoy writing about what they have done and can provide lengthy descriptions if given the time. This opens up opportunities for

reflection, through carefully chosen moments, by asking students why they did something in a particular way. We see from the data collected in Malta that even young children are happy to write about their experiences with robots and providing opportunities for this within workshops provides a route to engagement with reflection.

To introduce to students to reflection they could be asked to write a short account at the end of the first session about what they did, how they solved a particular puzzle or their greatest achievement. Tutors would then review these and write a question for each student to reflect upon at the start of the next workshop. Then at the end of workshop, they would be asked to write another description. These three short tasks would provide evidence not only of the children's experiences of the workshops for the purposes of evaluation but more importantly provide a pedagogic opportunity for students to develop their critical thinking and critical reflecting skills.

However difficulty arises when reflective activities are only done at the end of a workshop. This is particularly an issue when workshops only last one day and there are few opportunities for tutors to review and comment on reflections. Here the reflection can inform pupil voice activities (if implemented in the context of a regular lesson) or interviews in the case of research.

Although Papert speaks of 'writability', there is no reason that this could not be created through video or audio, with the task of documenting the construction or programming of robots becoming inter-twined with the robotics activity, particularly as documentation is an important part of STEM activities. This approach to reflection also allows us to consider students' ability to communicate with others, beyond their group and beyond the workshop. This aligns with the importance of developing communication skills as part of the 21st Century skill set that all learners need.

Over longer workshops, students could draw together their constructions and reflections to showcase what they have learned and achieved. Others could create a presentation or video giving their top 5 tips for competing in a competition or working as team, which could be shared with future workshop participants. An example of a showcase was created by one of the Greek teachers. An example of the later could be created during or at the end of the Botball competition to be shared with students participating in the following year's Botball preparation workshops, supporting a communal constructivist pedagogical approach (Girvan & Savage, 2010).

Although there are other structured opportunities for students to develop their communication skills, for example through presentations as mentioned in the activity plans (see D4.1 and D6.3), the other key opportunity for students to develop their communication skills is working in collaboration as part of a team.

For the purposes of this report we refer to team work rather than collaboration, as students may work as members of the same group or team but may not necessarily collaborate. There are a range of reasons for this as evidenced in the detailed case studies, however using the phrase teamwork also hints at the idea that several 21st Century skills are required for students to engage in team work, including communication and collaboration. Skills can also be sequences, with communication required before collaboration can take place. But team work hints at something more than working effectively together, highlighting that students don't always need to be working on the same thing at the same time to be constructively working towards a collective goal.

Concepts of teamwork and collaboration are complex and therefore encompass a variety of factors that need careful consideration. However, of the workshops and conferences reviewed in D1.1 only one (Robotixlab) mentioned developing teamwork skills and if we consider the research literature, it

is rare to find details on the social orchestration of the teams beyond the number of students per group. Details on whether teams were single or mixed gender are included for research purposes but there is rarely consideration of the effects that this might have.

From the review of workshops, literature and evaluation of the activity plans in the first project year; it is clear that there insufficient consideration of teaching, developing and supporting team work skills. There is often an assumption that students already know how to work in a team, however this is rarely the case, so students need to be introduced and taught skills. Those who have been introduced to teamwork will then need support to develop their skills. This may take the form of structured planning guides through which the team identifies tasks or roles and plans how they will complete the project and how they will support each other.

During the workshops, it was clear from the activity plans that tutors intended to monitor students' progress and provide support when students struggled to complete a task. However these were task orientated and did not consider the need to monitor interactions within the teams or provide supports and remedies for dysfunctional teams.

Reviewing the detailed case studies in this report it is clear to see an initial trend that mixed-gender groups have more difficulty functioning as an effective team than single-gender groups. Therefore with reference to the points above, different approaches or additional supports may be required for mixed-gender teams and need to be planned for. While an easy solution to this issue could be to only have single-sex groups, this would limit the impact of educational robotics on addressing gender stereotypes.

8 RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presents the recommendations emerging from the analysis of the data. The evidence for each recommendation has already been presented (sections 4-6) and discussed (section 7) to allow for the clear presentation of recommendations here. Each is presented with a topic heading and specific recommendations for affected work packages. Recommendations for the Framework (WP1) will typically require a corresponding element in the Activity Plan (WP4) and Repository (WP5). There are also recommendations for the evaluation of ER4STEM going forward.

12. Use 21st Century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills.
 - a. **Framework** – develop a unit within the Framework on 21st Century skills which is sub-divided into sections on teamwork and collaboration, communication, creativity and critical thinking.
 - b. **Activity Plan** – highlight the importance of teaching and developing 21st Century skills by including prompts and examples within the objectives, social orchestration, student productions, sequence of activities and evaluation.
 - c. **Evaluation** – merge analysis of industry skills and soft-skills under the heading of 21st Century skills, adjusting research questions and focus accordingly; and sub-divide into sections on teamwork and collaboration, communication, creativity and critical thinking.

13. Consider creativity as leading to innovation and entrepreneurship

- a. **Framework** – consider how creativity can be fostered in different forms, through different activities at different scales and provide a frame.
 - b. **Activity Plan** – provide examples of how creativity can be fostered using the year 1 evaluation findings.
 - c. **Evaluation** – merge innovation and entrepreneurship in data collection and analysis.
14. Examine critical thinking through a focus on reflective thinking
- a. **Framework** – consider how critical thinking can be fostered in different forms, through different activities at different scales and provide a frame.
 - b. **Activity Plan** – highlight the importance of teaching and developing critical thinking through reflection by including prompts within the objectives, social orchestration, student productions, sequence of activities and evaluation; provide examples of critical thinking activities using reflective tools; integrate reflection in student productions.
 - c. **Evaluation** – provide flexibility within the evaluation for a range of reflective tools to be used; work with WP4 and WP2 to develop tools which can be used to meet requirements and provide evidence of learning.
15. Provide evidence of learning
- a. **Framework** – explain how artefacts of learning can be used to evidence learning.
 - b. **Activity Plan** – include examples of achievable and measurable objectives; provide examples of how student productions (artefacts of learning) and reflections (as a form of student production) can demonstrate achievement in a range of objectives, including domain, technical and 21st Century skills.
 - c. **Evaluation** – collate examples of measurable objectives and how students can evidence their achievement of these objectives through their productions and reflections; use these to analyse learner engagement in subsequent years.
16. Differentiate activities
- a. **Framework** – consider how differentiation can be integrated.
 - b. **Activity Plan** – within student productions, teaching methods and the sequence and description of activities, prompt activity designers to consider differentiation, providing examples of how this can be achieved in relation to sample objectives.
 - c. **Evaluation** – review activity plans and wider workshop data to identify and analyse the use by tutors and uptake by students of differentiated activities; track students to questionnaire data to assess impact and compare with previous years.
17. Developing new entry points
- a. **Framework** – increase the types of entry point in the non-goal orientated domain; develop non-gendered activities; provide opportunities for a creative and/or fictitious elements; offer routes for students to rapidly develop their own problems to solve and to make the workshop personally meaningful.
 - b. **Activity Plan** – highlight alternative entry points by including this aspect in the student learning process with examples; similarly include suggestions and examples within the first phase of the sequence and description of activities

9 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, there are clear recommendations emerging from the first year evaluation. To meet the objectives of the project, baseline questions were identified. While only some of these could be answered, those that could not clarified areas for development within the project which in-turn informed the recommendations. Additionally, it was shown that the evaluation criteria could be met through analysis of the evaluation data collected, showing that the evaluation pre-kit meets the requirements of the project.

10 SUMMARY

This deliverable has reported on the analysis and evaluation of the ER4STEM project in year 1. Data collected using the pre-kit (D6.1) in workshops implemented in year 1 (WP2; D2.1) were analysed using a range of approaches. Findings have been presented at 3 levels of analysis, before drawing the findings together by discussing the answers to the baseline questions, outcomes with regard to the evaluation criteria and unexpected findings. From this discussion, 10 recommendations have been made for the development of the ER4STEM project in years 2 and 3.

11 CONCLUSION / OUTLOOK

The next step is to present these findings to project partners as part of the discussions around the development of the ER4STEM Framework, Activity Plans, Repository and Evaluation, affecting WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6.

12 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for STEM
REA	Research Executive Agency
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

